

Blockchain Enabled Authentication System for Edge and Fog Computing

by

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Declaration of Authorship

I, Otuekong Idorenyin Umoren, declare that this thesis titled, "Blockchain Enabled Authentication System for Edge and Fog Computing" and the work presented in it are my own. I confirm that:

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- I have acknowledged all main sources of help.
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Abstract

Low-cost IoT sensors are widely used but face significant challenges in data quality, scalability, reliability, and security, particularly in distributed edge and fog computing environments. While edge and fog computing aim to improve device performance and data analytics, they inherit limitations from cloud computing, making this environment vulnerable to attacks. Current authentication methods in these environments often struggle with resource consumption, scalability, and security issues. Existing blockchain-based solutions, such as those using ethereum, have shown promise in addressing some of these challenges. However, they still face limitations in transaction speed, energy efficiency, and scalability when applied to edge and fog computing environments. Furthermore, there is a lack of comprehensive approaches that integrate user-specific data for secure registration and authentication while maintaining efficiency in resource-constrained environments. This research addresses the gaps in edge and fog computing environments and explores the utilisation of blockchain technologies and their application in edge and fog authentication systems. The study focusses on overcoming the scalability and security limitations inherent in current edge and fog computing environments, with potential applications in 6G-enabled IoT environments. By investigating these areas, this research seeks to contribute to the understanding of authentication and privacy in decentralised edge and fog computing environments, potentially providing a framework for leveraging blockchain technologies to improve security, scalability, and efficiency in next-generation computing systems.

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List of Abbreviations

6G	Sixth generation cellular network technology
Bdata	Biometric data
BlockChainNet	Blockchain Network
BlockchainUser	Blockchain User
DID	Decentralised Identifiers
Digkey	Digital key
DigS	Digital signature
Ds	Digital signature
DLT	Distributed Ledger Technology
EdgeDev	Edge Device
EthAcc	Ethereum Account
EthAdr	Ethereum address
EVM	The Ethereum Virtual computer
Fd	Fog Device
Fdi	Fog Device Identifier
Fdid	Fog Device Decentralised Identity
Fdc	Fog Device Configuration
Fdinfo	Fog Device Information
Fdname	Fog Device Name
Holder	Identity holder
ID	Digital Identity

Iinfo	Issuer Info
Issuer	Identity Issuer
LAMAS	Lightweight anonymous mutual authentication scheme
MFA	Multifactor Authentication
NeoAdr	Neo Address
PriKey	Private Key
PubKey	Public key
RegHd	Register Holder Device
ReqIdis	Identity Issuer Request
ReqIdv	Identity Verifier Request
SHA256	Online hash function
Sk	Session Key
SmartContract	Smart Contract
SSI	Self-Sovereign Identification
SSI-IoT	Self-Sovereign Identification Security in Internet of Things
Ui	User or Holder
UserEthAdr	User Ethereum Address
Usermail	User email Address
UserNeoAdr	User Neo Address
Userz	Multiple Users
Verifier	Identity Verifier
Vinfo	Verifier information
Wallet	Digital wallet

Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Motivation

Low-cost sensors in IoT have been deemed cheap and effective since the cost of data collection in IoT, quality of measurements, and reliability of the information they collect are limited. Collecting and processing data and running cloud services require computational resources to secure and protect data from malicious entities. These data are considered vulnerable to breaches and need to be secure from malicious entities; this, at this moment, makes authentication essential in fog computing [2]. The increase in cyber-attacks on various services has demonstrated the importance of secure and robust authentication systems. Notable attacks such as the IoT security breach in Amazon's ring home camera, where assailants successfully gained unauthorised access to many families' home monitoring systems and connected doorbells [5]. The hackers exploited some weak, recycled and default credentials and gained access to see and communicate or harass the customers remotely through the feeds from the cameras and devices integrated with microphones and speakers around their homes.

In March 2021, a cloud-based video surveillance service called Verkada was hacked. The assailants gained access to private information belonging to Verkada software clients. They had access to live video feeds of over 150,000 cameras mounted in hospitals, factories, schools and prisons using authorised admin account credentials found on the internet [6]. It was later discovered that over 100 employees have "super admin" privileges, which enabled them to gain access to thousands of customer cameras, this revealed the risks associated with over-privileged users.

Security in IoT is critical, primarily due to the wide range of security threats on networks. Additionally, there are insecure practices of individuals, users, groups, or organisations who lack or have limited resources or knowledge of practices to protect their IoT systems or architecture. Despite the limited resources of some IoT devices or edge devices, they can still be exploited through malware [7].

Other cyber attacks that target IoT systems include the attack on Dyn servers on 21 October 2016; this server controlled most domain name system infrastructure on the internet, leaving several websites, including Netflix, CNN, Twitter, and others, down in the United States and Europe. This distributed denial of service attack was carried out using a network of IoT devices infected with a Mirai botnet coordinated to flood the server with traffic till it collapsed [8]. The introduction of Fog computing does not mitigate attacks that target IoT devices, it introduces challenges makes the computing network vulnerable to more attacks such as malware and man-in-the-middle attacks [9]. Therefore, good authentication and data security mechanisms are highly required for many fog computing use cases. Fog computing Limitations and risks will be discussed in chapter 2.

Cloud computing has several benefits but also has limitations and challenges. By managing the underlying infrastructure, which includes hardware and software, cloud providers are able to reduce the cost of IT operations. Their primary role in data management often results in more reliable and secure services than traditional corporate data centres. By being universal, practical, incredibly scalable, and accessible, cloud computing accelerates the time it takes to develop and deploy software applications. However, challenges still need to be addressed, and these include privacy and security of data, risk of data confidentiality, data management problems, interoperability, service availability, latency on the network, lack of scalable storage, cloud downtime, cloud integrity, denial of service attacks, data loss or theft and data leakage [10]. Authentication is an essential step in ensuring the security of data stored on cloud servers. Controlled access to data, services, and resources provides improved security. Unfortunately, these centralised databases or third-party authentication solutions are vulnerable to attacks[11].

Authentication is said to be a critical factor which guarantees the security of data stored on cloud servers. This guarantees security through controlled access to data, services and resources. However, these authentication systems using a centralised database or a trusted third party are vulnerable to various cyber-attacks and breaches [11]. In IoT, devices generate large amounts of data in relatively less time, and these data are transferred from multiple IoT devices to the cloud through the internet simultaneously, causing network congestion at times. Fog computing was introduced to overcome the drawbacks and limitations related to IoT and the cloud. The fog environment operates between the cloud data and edge devices. These fog devices are commonly referred to as fog nodes, which are deployed with distributed ownership [12]. Generally, authentication, authorisation, and access control systems guarantee the security of all data types collected and saved on cloud servers. Secure

authentication is provided through methods of restriction and access control to data and various services [11].

Fog computing still relies on the cloud for authentication. The use of blockchain technology can help reduce this dependence, saving computation and network costs whilst achieving traceability. The unique characteristics of blockchain technology, such as transparency, secure encryption, reliability, mutual authentication between nodes, the use of a distributed encrypted ledger, and distributed database in which operations are executed would be beneficial to fog-based authentication [13]. Fog computing and blockchain technology both have distributed features that improve their functionality in different ways. Their distributed designs give room for trustworthy and decentralised systems. Because blockchain is distributed, it may be used with fog computing to provide secure payment methods, identity verification, and secure data management [14]. The distinctive features of fog computing, namely the ability to compute data, the distributed nature of fog devices and the properties of blockchain technology, such as the smart contract, decentralised ledger, and authentication systems, would take advantage of these features and properties and ensure secure authentication in a cloud and IoT environment.

The characteristics of edge and fog devices, such as low latency, make them capable of processing information without the involvement of the cloud server [15]. However, there are security challenges and limitations in edge and fog computing which include trust, security, and privacy due to its untrusted decentralised environment [2]. Authentication systems in edge and fog computing environments would benefit from the unique characteristics of blockchain technology such as the distribution of nodes, the decentralised storage, privacy, and smart contracts, ensuring secure authentication and mitigating cyber-attacks. Recently, some studies [16–18] have been introduced to overcome these issues and address the fog-based IoT limitations.

1.2 Problem Statement

This thesis addresses critical challenges in edge and fog computing, focusing on authentication, data privacy, scalability, and security. The research aims to design a blockchain-based solution for edge and fog computing environments. This solution will optimise resource usage in computation, storage, and networking while ensuring data integrity, privacy, and trustworthiness. The proposed system seeks to enhance scalability and secure authentication within edge and fog computing infrastructures, addressing the challenges and requirements of these distributed computing paradigms.

1.3 Research Questions

The thesis explores the difficulties associated with secure authentication, data privacy and scalability in edge and fog computing and investigates solutions to improve authentication and privacy. To address the following research questions, this research proposed an architecture for secure authentication in edge and fog computing.

- **Question 1: What are the challenges related to secure authentication in edge and fog computing environments?** To answer this question, this thesis explores the research gaps in secure authentication in edge and fog computing environments.
- **Question 2: What are the existing solutions proposed to improve secure authentication and data privacy in edge and fog computing?** To address this question, this thesis investigates existing approaches to improve authentication, data privacy and security of

services, and proposes a secure authentication system using ethereum blockchain technology in an edge and fog computing environment.

- **Question 3: How can secure authentication, performance and scalability be improved in the proposed system?** To address this question, an improved secure authentication system is proposed utilising neo blockchain in an edge and fog computing environment.

1.4 Research Objectives

This thesis seeks to better understand the difficulties associated with secure authentication in edge and fog computing settings by developing a system to improve secure authentication. To address the research questions, the proposed systems will take into account the following objectives:

- Conduct a comprehensive literature review of edge, fog, cloud computing, and blockchain technology, highlighting the security challenges and existing solutions in IoT, edge and fog computing environments.
- Identify gaps and drawbacks in existing systems and discuss potential improvements in edge and fog computing environments.
- Develop a blockchain-based system to improve authentication, security, privacy, and scalability in edge and fog computing environments.
- Develop a system to improve authentication, security and privacy in a blockchain-enabled edge and fog computing environments using self-sovereign identification approach.
- Execute experiments and present comparative results, analysis and discussions.

1.5 Summary of Contributions

- A decentralised user authentication system was designed and implemented using Ethereum smart contract. It aimed to address user authentication in a decentralised environment and address fog computing security problems inherited from IoT and cloud computing. It provided a solution for immutability, scale-ability problems in fog computing and proposed the use of conventional authentication in a fog and a blockchain environment to achieve the distributed authentication system. Compared to other methods, the proposed system utilised commonly used authentication factors to ensure easy adoption in real-world applications. Experimental results revealed that the proposed method achieved performance improvement, used less resources in Ethereum (ether) and could be scaled to more devices and relatively used less resources when compared to existing methods.
- A Neo blockchain smart contract is created and implemented to address secure authentication and other limitations in an IoT and fog computing environment. This included scalability, immutability, and secure authentication of fog devices in a decentralised fog computing environment. The research also aimed to improve the previous work, which utilised an Ethereum smart contract to provide a decentralised secure fog computing environment. The comparison has shown that with the advantages of the Neo blockchain, performance, speed, and security have improved over the Ethereum blockchain.
- A novel scheme to enhance user verification and data security in a Lightweight Anonymous Mutual Authentication Scheme(LAMAS) by leveraging a self-sovereign identification scheme under fog computing scenario. The proposed scheme utilises the Ethereum blockchain and

smart contract technology to securely register and verify digital identities. By leveraging the advantages of self-sovereign identification, such as privacy, transparency, and decentralization, the potential to enhance the overall security posture of LAMAS has been demonstrated. The effectiveness of the proposed scheme has been evaluated through experiments conducted on the Ethereum blockchain environment.

1.6 Thesis Organisation

The structure of this thesis is as follows:

- Chapter 2 presents the literature review on edge and fog computing, cloud computing, distributed ledger technology. The chapter then presents existing work which utilised methods to improve secure authentication in edge and fog computing environment, and a review on research gaps hereby addressing research questions 1, and 2.
- Chapter 3 presents the conceptual proposed system in this thesis to improve secure authentication and the implementation process of a decentralised authentication system utilising ethereum blockchain technology to enhance secure authentication in fog computing, hereby addressing question 3.
- Chapter 4 presents the implementation of a decentralised authentication system utilising neo blockchain technology to improve the existing blockchain-based authentication in fog computing environment, hereby addressing question 3.

- Chapter 5 presents and discusses the implementation of the secure verification scheme utilising self-sovereign identification method in a fog-cloud computing environment to enhance the overall security posture of LAMAS, hereby addressing question 3.
- The work outlined in this thesis is concluded in Chapter 6. Following a summary of the contributions, recommendations are made for the future course of this work's relevant study.

1.7 List of Publications

The following publications are the result of this study:

- Umoren, O., Singh, R., Pervez, Z. and Dahal, K., 2022. Securing fog computing with a decentralised user authentication approach based on blockchain. *Sensors*, 22(10), p.3956. (Chapter 3)
- Umoren, O., Singh, R., Awan, S., Pervez, Z. and Dahal, K., 2022. Blockchain-based secure authentication with improved performance for fog computing. *Sensors*, 22(22), p.8969. (Chapter 4)
- Umoren, O. and Marco-Gisbert, H., 2020. A Study on the Security of Authentication Systems. *UBICOMM 2020: The Fourteenth International Conference on Mobile Ubiquitous Computing, Systems, Services and Technologies*.

Chapter 2

Background and Related Work

2.1 Introduction

This chapter discusses key concepts related to this research, which include cloud computing, edge and fog computing architecture, blockchain technology, authentication systems, and identity management systems. It also examines existing research in edge and fog computing-related areas, explores methods to enhance secure authentication in fog computing, and conducts a review of research gaps. The chapter addresses research questions 1 and 2, setting the stage for a detailed analysis in these areas.

2.2 Cloud Computing

'Cloud computing' is the phrase used to describe the provision of computer services that are administered by online data centres and where its customers will simply pay a fixed rate to have access to a certain amount of capabilities that are provided by cloud providers like Microsoft Azure [19], Huawei Cloud

[20] or Amazon Web Services [21]. Over the past few years, cloud computing has been gaining popularity and developed into an effective and economical computing model. It can be numbered among the innovations that have most influenced computers since their existence [22]. In 2020, Huawei Cloud crafted hybrid cloud solutions for media organisations and broadcasters to reduce both storage capacities and application usage. It works with business customers, partners, and developers to create new and upgraded technologies for the cloud and to lay the foundations for a world in which ‘every cloud is ubiquitous cloud, and every intelligence is pervasive intelligence.’ [20] Using cloud computing, they can get as many computational resources as they need, whenever they need it, without having to buy and maintain an on-site, physical IT infrastructure. Cost efficiency, flexibility, and scalability are just a few advantages of cloud computing over traditional computing techniques. Using cloud computing services provided by Infrastructure as a Service(IaaS), Software as a Service(SaaS), and Platform as a Service(PaaS). Three different divisions of cloud computing architecture, users shall require less in-house IT and can scale their infrastructure up or down depending on changes in demand [23]. Cloud computing architecture provides hybrid cloud architecture in order to accommodate private and public cloud users from different points of view. The hybrid cloud is an approach that allows users to access servers, storage, databases, and a variety of application services online.

Many computing infrastructures have historically grown and expanded due to breakthroughs and rapid changes in technologies, including parallel computing. Parallel computing gave rise to the fast-evolving cloud computing technology, and because of its numerous benefits, monitoring centre computer platforms have now incorporated innovative features and concepts, piqued the interest of academics in various sectors [24]. To meet the growing demand for

computing resources, cloud computing is constantly evolving, enabling customers to purchase specific sets of resources and only pay for their use. As information technology advanced, the concept of allowing access to computing resources emerged. Now, cloud computing is a leading business model for supplying IT infrastructure, components, and applications. Cloud computing allows a disruptive transition from IT-as-a-product to IT-as-a-service, transforming an IT provisioning model that was formerly product-centric into one that is global, dispersed, and service-centric [25].

Data processing, education and research, services for small and medium-sized businesses, e-learning, augmented reality, manufacturing scenarios, building management, smart city, emergency recovery, entertainment, digital government, human resource management, Internet of Cars and Internet of Devices, health, civil protection and safety, home automation – just to mention some of those. A cloud computing service is a catalogue of standardised services or components offered for use or consumption by other services or components. These components can produce higher-level services, which may then be offered as services to even higher-level service components. A service is an abstracted resource (e.g., machine, storage, software) hierarchically offered for use or consumption by higher-level data, services, or system components. Overall, IoT and cloud computing have grown in this world very fast and globally. Also, once they are combined, they both show a trait that excels and is extremely important to each other, figure 2.1 illustrates cloud, edge, fog computing hierarchy . As a result of the current extensive research in developing cloud computation capabilities and storage, more and more cloud computing and Internet of Things (IoT) apps are designed to work side by side to produce data and gather data at the same time by benefiting from cloud computing and storage as stated in reference [26].

FIGURE 2.1: Illustration of Cloud, Edge and Fog Computing Hierarchy.

People and businesses have access to controlled shared IT resources like servers, storage and applications that can be scalable through a shared network on demand using cloud computing categories [23]. The need for infrastructure and storage has grown, which has been crucial in meeting that demand. One remarkable capability of cloud computing is its ability to deliver resources like hardware and software through a network. In cloud computing, numerous resources are available for hire and are charged for each use. Figure 2.2 shows a simple cloud computing architecture. The cloud can be broadly divided into four categories [27]:

1. Private cloud: This category of cloud is created to meet the specific needs of an institution, it functions just for the need of that institution.

FIGURE 2.2: Cloud Computing Architecture.

2. Public cloud: Public clouds are created by cloud providers such as Google, Amazon and Microsoft. They are made ready for any institution or the public access to the infrastructure and services. These resources are shared among several users.
3. Community cloud: A community cloud is considered a shared cloud where users and institutions with similar interests are granted access to the infrastructure and services.
4. Hybrid cloud: These clouds combine the properties of private and public clouds. However, with their integration, each cloud maintains its identity, facilitating various deployments.

2.3 Fog Computing

The phrase "fog computing" was first used by Cisco. It is a modern technology that offers many benefits, particularly for the Internet of Things. Similar to how the cloud does, fog computing affords IoT clients storage and statistics processing abilities. In comparison to cloud computing, fog computing specialises in giving fog devices access to records processing and storage regionally. The term 'Fog nodes' is used to describe these gadgets inside the fog computing community. They can be any tool with the ability to estimate, store, and hook up with the net, inclusive of embedded servers, production controllers, hubs, modems, and safety cameras. The networking, computing, and storage assets are to be had in each fog, and the cloud [28]. Fog is generally defined as a disbursed, decentralised computing system that lets groups interact from a variety of places, which includes hubs, airports, hospitals, and colleges. Several fog gadgets are held via numerous entities. It is occasionally known as a virtualized environment that manages the distribution, storage, and processing of assets in cloud computing centres whilst closing partially outdoors the network area. Fog computing is regularly thought of as an extension of the cloud that is located near IoT or edge gadgets with confined resources. They are situated in various geographical areas with community connectivity, and processing power [29].

The Internet of Things (IoT) makes use of fog computing to improve performance, efficiency, and the amount of data that needs to be transported to the cloud for processing, analysis, and storage. The information that the sensors have gathered will, therefore, be received and analysed by network edge devices [28]. This gives a better solution for the enhancement of cloud-dependent services and aids in overcoming processing limits in edge, cloud, and Internet of Things (IoT) devices. In order to reduce network traffic or

connection with the cloud, edge and IoT devices are provided with cloud computing services. As a result, the data collected or acquired by edge devices are processed quickly and delivered to the cloud [18]. Any entity can contribute their devices as Fog devices to a network that uses decentralised, distributed, and scalable fog computing to process IoT applications. Each device, however, lacks a reliable connection. The primary attributes of fog computing are described in [30] as given below:

- **Adaptability:** These are composed of several edge and fog devices that provide storage and do computations.
- **Real-time communications:** Real-time communication between fog nodes and with relevant data deployed in the cloud is made possible by fog computing.
- **Physical distribution:** Fog computing offers applications and services that are decentralised.
- **Less latency:** Fog computing's closeness to the edge devices reduces information computing time with the edge devices and aids position responsiveness to host fog devices on several locations.
- **Compatibility:** Fog modules are made to function across a variety of platforms and service providers.
- **Web analytics and cloud integration:** For the computation and data processing near the edge devices, the fog's location between the cloud and the devices is essential.
- **Heterogeneity:** Because fog nodes and edge devices are manufactured by various companies and have distinct properties, it is essential that their hosting be based on those qualities.

To take advantage of the economies of scale that the pay-as-you-go cloud model offers, fog computing suggests that the data generated by end devices be processed or pre-processed. This is primarily done to reduce activity and raw data sets travelling across the network on their route to cloud services. Naturally, this necessitates some provisioning of hardware resources at the network's edge outside of the cloud. This would enable the processing of latency-sensitive parts locally, such as SLA (Service Level Agreement) compliance, while other computationally heavy or delay-tolerant processes take place in the cloud [14]. Fog computing does not address the privacy and security concerns associated with data transportation and, hence, dispersed computing, as well as the shortcomings and downsides of current approaches.

2.4 Edge Computing

The edge computing paradigm handles computation at the network's edge; this is different when compared to the typical cloud computing model, with its primary goal being to bring computation closer to the source of data. Edge computing at the edge of the network includes data generation, service delivery, and computation. This involves the extension of the network, computing, storage, and resource capabilities from the cloud to the edge of the network, offering intelligent services there to meet the needs of IT industries. These needs include flexible connectivity, real-time data analytics, data optimisation, security, and privacy, and guarantee the demands for low latency and high bandwidth on the network [31]. Edge computing significantly reduces delays in data processing through the deployment of storage resources closer to users or customers. On the other hand, edge devices can handle some tasks directly because they do not require the capabilities of a cloud server, and they can simultaneously protect sensitive data and maintain user and data

privacy through the reduction of user data being transferred over the core network and implementing encryption and anonymisation techniques locally [32]. These advantages have increased the growth of edge computing in recent years.

However, the Internet of Things (IoT) has introduced high demands in the transmission bandwidth, latency, consumption of energy, performance of applications, and reliability. Meeting these high-performance needs brings challenges due to the constrain of bandwidth, high latency and energy consumption in the centralised processing system of cloud computing [33]. Figure 2.3 shows an architecture for cloud computing comprising the edge and fog computing layers. More issues have been discovered in cloud computing because of IoT's ongoing development and wide use. For example, when data produced by global terminal devices is computed and stored in a centralised cloud, it results in issues which include low throughput, high latency, bandwidth bottlenecks, data privacy, vulnerabilities connected to centralised storage, and additional costs such as transmission cost, energy cost, calculation cost and storage costs. Many applications of IoT, especially in the area of Internet of Vehicles (IoV), require high-speed, low-latency, quick data processing, analysis, and result delivery [34].

FIGURE 2.3: Illustration of Cloud, Edge and Fog Computing Architecture.

Fortunately, it's been predicted that tens of billions of edge nodes will be installed in the coming years and will take advantage of edge computing technology. Its architectural concepts to improve technologies such as 5G. This offers methods to integrate a good number of unused resources scattered across the network's edge to provide services for consumers easily [33]. Edge computing has gained a good amount of attention and has been suggested as a solution to the drawbacks of cloud computing. The idea behind edge computing is the movement of data processing, storage, and computing tasks previously handled on the cloud to the network's edge close to user devices. This, in turn, reduces the time required to transfer data between devices and through networks, speeds up device responses, lowers the cost of data transmission, and promotes decentralisation [35]. However, edge computing has

drawbacks and limitations, which include scalability, interoperability, latency variability, reliability and fault Tolerance. These drawbacks make implementation and integration of edge computing on a bigger scale difficult. Along with maintenance costs, deploying and sustaining edge devices at a bigger scale may be high [36]. Several studies have proposed different systems that utilise edge computing and its properties and suggested ways to mitigate its limitations and drawbacks.

2.4.1 Characteristics of Edge and Fog Computing

The shift in computation from cloud computing closer to the edge is a major factor prompting the transition from cloud computing to edge and fog computing. Fog computing has properties which include a range of applications and IoT devices [37]. It has various geographically distributed nodes, low latency, and other properties [38]. The establishment of trust in the edge and fog environment can be a challenge because each device has its specific purpose based on its properties and capabilities. Both cloud computing and IoT benefit from edge and fog computing in many ways. The main properties of edge and fog computing include the following [30]:

1. **Compatibility:** Fog computing systems are made to be integrated and implemented on several platforms and service providers.
2. **Location awareness:** Edge and fog computing enables the placement of fog nodes in different geographical regions, which grants knowledge about the location of end devices. The close proximity of the end devices reduces latency during data transfer and processing. Edge and fog

computing support the collection and processing of data in a location-dependent method, which is different from the conventional method of data transfer and processing in the cloud [39].

3. **Adaptability:** This offers and allocates storage resources to manage computational operations in real-time, thus taking advantage of many network sensors, as well as edge and fog devices.
4. **Physical distribution:** This provides a decentralised environment that supports applications and services hosted in different or multiple locations.
5. **Low latency:** This is the minimum time required to execute computational requests. The closeness of fog nodes to edge devices supports faster response time [38].
6. **Heterogeneity:** Fog computing can effectively support a diverse range of software and hardware components, hereby making deployment across various environments possible [39]. Hosting fog nodes and edge devices and taking advantage of their properties are essential, considering their unique functionalities.
7. **Multi-Tenancy:** This is the inherent capability of a system to accommodate many instances simultaneously while sharing a single instance of the platform. These are commonly known as shared systems. The adoption of the fog platform can be attributed to its distributed and high level of virtualization nature [38].
8. **Web analytics and cloud integration:** The processing of data close to the edge of the network depends on the fog node's position, this removes the gap between the cloud and the edge devices.

9. Geographical distribution: In edge computing, the use of multiple geographically separated edge computing nodes to facilitate the sharing of data and resources is employed. This enables effective collaboration between device owners and users, particularly in scenarios with privacy concerns or if the costs associated with data transmission are significant or large, [39].
10. Interoperability and federation: The fog computing paradigm has the capability to support a wide range of hardware and software components, thereby enabling its deployment across various environments [39]. To enhance the transparency and compatibility of fog computing with other systems, open standards are necessary. This involves enabling third-party systems to execute models and processes via web service calls.

2.4.2 Edge and Fog Computing Use Cases and Applications

The aim of edge and fog computing is to distribute computational operations to enhance data processing and the fast delivery of services in IoT. These services are provided at the local area network (LAN) layer. Consequently, the rapid expansion of IoT devices and data presents drawbacks and limitations in the areas of security, trust, and privacy [38].

1. Authentication and Identity Management System: Through the creation of resource-sharing protocols, employing safe authentication protocols, and the establishment of mutual authentication, edge and fog computing can be utilised for authentication purposes. In edge and fog computing use cases, the use of this system can aid in guaranteeing safe connections between users and servers. Through the storage and management of

user identities on a blockchain that is accessible to authorised parties only, the system [18] makes use of blockchain and smart contract to provide effective and secure communication between fog nodes and to automate the identification verification procedure in the fog computing environment. This use case directly supports the proposed methodology in this thesis.

2. Self-Sovereign Identification (SSI): This is a method that involves the creation of digital identity, which is important when considering identity verification in IoT. Edge and fog computing support data processing close to the network's edge and lessen the burden on centralised resources, which may be utilised to support SSI. Blockchain technology has been leveraged to provide safe and effective communication between edge and fog devices and smart home gadgets [40]. The system is designed to store and manage identities on a private blockchain that are only available to those with permission. The scheme also utilises smart contracts to automate the identity verification procedure. This use case directly supports the proposed methodology in this thesis.
3. Medical wearables: Healthcare providers' utilisation of edge devices is increasingly prevalent. The technology is employed in the provision of telemedicine services, the monitoring of patient's health status [41], and the guidance of on-site medical personnel during surgical procedures. Edge and Fog computing has emerged as a critical component in the domain of healthcare, particularly in the context of real-time processing. Smart e-health monitoring systems have been proposed by several authors [42, 43] utilising smart gateways to connect the sensor layer

to cloud services, which have functionalities such as data mining, distributed storage, and notification services at the periphery of the network. The utilisation of numerous servers within a fog computing environment, enabling the execution of a specific application, has resulted in the enhancement of healthcare services. Fog computing offers numerous benefits to healthcare systems, such as the reduction of energy usage, as well as the mitigation of delays and data traffic. Furthermore, the analysis and storage of data at the fog layer contribute to heightened security measures, as it enables the preservation of critical and confidential information inside the confines of the organisation.

4. Traffic control systems: Fog computing and vehicle networks have supplanted traditional physical traffic signal systems with virtual traffic light systems, offering a more economically efficient alternative. An integrated system was proposed with the aim of enhancing the safety and security of transportation, providing a highly comfortable and secure environment for all individuals involved, and mitigating the occurrence of fatal incidents [44]. In this study, machine learning techniques were employed to enhance the efficacy of communication between intelligent transport systems (ITS) and human users. The realization of this objective can be facilitated by the implementation of sixth-generation (6G) networks and the progression of vehicular Ad hoc networks (VANETs). Furthermore, fog computing offers a convenient means to alleviate traffic congestion by employing traffic signal adjustments that are responsive to the prevailing traffic conditions and facilitating the use of vehicular communications to guide cars towards less congested routes.

5. Smart grid systems: Smart grids facilitate the management and operation of interconnected devices through machine-to-machine and human-to-machine communication. This enables a high level of quality of service, reduction in failure rates, enhancement of energy efficiency, and optimisation of security measures [38]. Edge and fog computing have been integrated into the smart grid as presented in this novel algorithm for real-time virtual machine (VM) migration with the objective of load balancing in fog computing environments. The increase in the popularity of fog computing has opened the way for efficient resource management techniques to ensure optimal utilisation of resources and improved system performance. Load balancing is considered essential to accomplishing these goals by sharing the burden among fog nodes equally. Their proposed algorithm focused on addressing the challenges of load balancing in a fog environment by ensuring efficient utilisation of resources, achieving maximum throughput and optimising response time [45].
6. Inter-connected vehicles: Fog computing facilitates a secure and efficient real-time interaction among autos, traffic signals, and access points by leveraging context awareness. Consequently, the provision of vehicle-to-vehicle communication is facilitated by the close proximity of fog nodes to IoT devices. The vehicles operating within the context of Vehicular hoc networks (VANETs) necessitate services that exhibit minimal latency and facilitate short-distance domestic connections. These requirements can be effectively met through the use of fog. Systems have been proposed [46, 47] utilising fog computing and VANET for vehicle security and traffic management.
7. Smart homes and cities: The utilisation of smart-city applications is to optimise a functional urban system to provide immediate feedback on any issues that may arise in users' operations. Despite the existence

of various cloud-based solutions for smart cities, they fail to fully address limitations and drawbacks. These limitations and drawbacks are latency, mobility support, scalability, and localisation of data computation. Various architectural frameworks have been proposed to mitigate the drawbacks within a standard Computing Environment of Smart Cities. The architectural framework [48] presents the utilisation of all computing tiers, cloud, fog, and edge within a city's infrastructure. This framework outlines the deployment strategies for various types of services across each tier.

8. Data management: The use of more devices in IoT has brought about a significant increase in the volume of data, and the less effectiveness of cloud computing in data management due to limitations has made the adoption of fog computing necessary, which is an advantage due to its proximity to edge devices in the network[49].
9. Network management: Network management in fog computing involves the provision of support for Software-Defined Networks (SDN) and Network Function Virtualization (NFV), the mitigation of congestion in the main network and the assurance of dependable network connectivity. The utilisation of fog computing presents a solution for diverting network traffic from the central database, hence mitigating latency and enhancing the overall performance of the network [50]. In addition, they suggest the use of artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) methodologies for the purpose of enhancing network management in fog computing environments.

2.4.3 Challenges in Edge and Fog Computing

The advancement in edge and fog computing technology has addressed some challenges associated with cloud computing, thereby improving communication. However, it is important to note that edge and fog computing has its challenges, limitations and drawbacks, which pose risks to data security and privacy. The current security measures in cloud computing are considered not suitable for fog computing due to their properties, which include decentralisation, heterogeneity, and geo-distribution [51]. Therefore, an advanced security method must be developed to address the requirements of edge and fog computing. Despite the advantages fog computing offers, it also comes with its own security limitations and drawbacks that may make the implementation of current authentication systems difficult. The distributed nature of edge and fog computing has its disadvantages, such as the devices with high computational power being able to function as fog nodes. However, it is necessary to understand that not all the nodes have the capabilities to fulfil the requirements of data processing. As a result, the use of all-purpose function beyond its aim may be a possible challenge.

Additionally, when considering the aim of service, the development of large-scale applications may provide challenges due to the constrained resources of certain edge devices and fog nodes. Hereby creates room which requires developing a platform that eases the development of distributed applications. The implementation of a security system with the aim of ensuring the integrity of data operations can have a good impact on the quality of service provided by edge and fog computing environments. Furthermore, the implementation of authentication systems to ensure security and privacy in a distributed network can introduce considerable challenges [38].

There are various additional challenges in the storage of data within IoT-based fog computing environment. These include [39]:

1. High Energy consumption: Edge devices often encounter challenges associated with high energy consumption.
2. Limited storage capacity: Edge devices often have limited storage, which can provide a significant challenge when it comes to storing large volumes of data.
3. Data security: The maintenance of data security and privacy poses a significant challenge in fog computing environments due to the frequent transfer of sensitive data over networks or the internet [37].
4. Data integrity: The maintenance of data integrity is of great significance, since any errors or corruption can have adverse effects on the precision and dependability of the data.
5. Data management: The function of managing and organising massive volumes of data can provide great challenges, particularly in situations where data is stored across various devices within a decentralised environment.
6. Data accessibility: The task of ensuring timely accessibility of data to authorised users can present challenges, particularly in situations where data is kept across various devices within a distributed computing environment.
7. Loss of data: IoT devices often encounter challenges when operating in fog computing environments, such as data discontinuity, limited coverage in unfamiliar areas, and the need for extensive data transmission [18]. These challenges can lead to errors in data transmission and general performance in edge and fog computing system.

2.5 Security Challenges and Threat Models in Edge and Fog Computing

Most applications of edge and fog computing are basically motivated by the user's need for functionality, which sometimes overlooks security requirements. The importance of addressing the security problems within edge and fog computing. The security vulnerabilities in edge and fog computing have been inherited from cloud computing [18]. The vulnerability of edge and fog computing to cyberattacks is attributed to its reliance on traditional network infrastructure. The vulnerability surrounding authentication and privacy can present challenges within edge and fog computing. The collaboration of fog nodes in a network has the potential to introduce vulnerabilities within the network, as a compromised node can compromise other nodes [52]. Various authentication, security and privacy concerns have been documented in the literature, discussing the inherent characteristics of fog computing, including heterogeneity, proximity to IoT devices, and the expansion of cloud computing. Edge and fog Computing are vulnerable to various forms of cyberattacks, including man-in-the-middle, denial-of-service, rogue fog node, spam, eavesdropping, Sybil attacks, etc. [53].

1. Sybil: A Sybil attack involves an assailant creating many fraudulent identities with the intention of undermining and breaching the security system of a network service and leveraging it in a disproportionate manner to create a more substantial impact [54]. The node that engages in impersonation is commonly known as the malicious node or Sybil attacker, whilst the node that assumes a false identity is commonly referred to as the Sybil node.

2. **Tampering:** This is a form of malicious attack where the assailant introduces a delay during data transmission, discards the data, or changes data [55]. The inherent mobility of fog computing introduces challenges in detecting attacks quickly, as different networks may lead to delays and disruptions in data transfer, hence making immediate identification of such attacks difficult.
3. **Spam:** This attack involves the assailant deceiving its victim through overloading them with data, therefore exploiting the vulnerability to get unauthorised access to the victim's network resources and compromise their privacy [56]. Spam attacks are widely recognised as a significant threat to internet and network users. Internet users face security challenges when they encounter unwanted communications, commonly known as spam.
4. **Eavesdropping:** This form of attack is also called snooping or sniffing, wherein the assailant engages in the surveillance and unauthorised monitoring of the target's data through network interception [57]. The vulnerability of wireless data transmission to eavesdropping is attributed to the inherent openness of the network. Consequently, the one who engages in eavesdropping can decipher the confidential data.
5. **Forgery:** This type of attack involves the imitation of a service, network or node by the assailant, to deceive users into executing actions as directed by the assailant [56]. However, such can have an adverse impact on the quality of service provided by networks, as it may result in decreased performance due to the use of bandwidth, storage, and energy resources.

6. Denial of service: This attack deprives legitimate users of authorised access to the service or network [58]. The network resources are significantly occupied by the attacker, resulting in a decline in the overall performance of the service hosted on the network. Due to the inherent resource constraints of edge devices, they encounter difficulties in effectively handling a substantial influx of data simultaneous.
7. Collusion: This form of attack manipulates and deceives a legitimate user of a service with the aim of preventing them from gaining access to a service or their due resources [59]. Moreover, this attack has the potential to compromise the victims' passwords, thereby granting the attacker access to files and other sensitive data.
8. Man-in-the-Middle: This cyberattack occurs when two nodes (node A and node B) communicate, and a third node positions itself between them [60]. This third node actively monitors the communication, records the transmitted data, and can manipulate the data without the knowledge of the communicating nodes. The execution of this attack needs limited resources on fog devices, specifically low CPU and memory utilisation. Consequently, conventional intrusion detection methods cannot identify a man-in-the-middle attack.
9. Impersonation: In this attack, the assailant assumes the identity of a legitimate fog node and proceeds to carry out services in a way that appears to originate from the legitimate node [61]. The use of this attack has emerged as a concern within cloud computing systems, most times attributed to the substantial allocation of system resources, the deployment configurations, and the decentralisation of user data.

10. Identity privacy: This guarantees the protection of the personal data or information of individuals or users involved in the communication process [53]. However, using decentralised authentication in fog computing, which needs the user details such as name, email address and phone number, may potentially leave the user with other vulnerabilities.
11. Data privacy: This is commonly known as information privacy and involves the establishment of guidelines for the management of data. Insufficient data privacy in edge and fog computing networks has the potential to exposure user data to untrusted nodes.
12. User privacy: This is the architectural framework in which users employ fog services to secure the confidentiality of their status and operational transactions within the network [62]. One potential strategy may involve the generation of tasks by fog clients and distributing them over multiple fog nodes.
13. Location privacy: This is the user's capacity to manage and regulate their past and current geographical data. F fog computing enables enhanced mobility, whereby edge devices continue to rely on their present or previously stored location. However, the reliance on location information may expose users to vulnerabilities. Some proposed approaches [18] used blockchain technology's properties to preserve the location privacy of fog nodes in a fog computing environment.

The most notable limitation or challenge is user authentication; notably, the conventional authentication methods are not optimally suited for the distinct architecture and characteristics of edge and fog computing. In addition, it should be noted that conventional authentication methods need a good number of computational resources and result in considerable latency, which fails to align with the fundamental demands of edge and fog computing. Other

limitations are identity management, physical attack limitations, physical and link layer security limitations, network layer attacks, transport and application layer limitations, multi-layered limitations, security limitations across the fog computing architecture and trust management in fog computing [63]. Fog computing systems can successfully address these drawbacks and limitations by integrating distributed ledger technologies, such as blockchain.

2.6 Blockchain Technology

Blockchain is a distributed ledger technology that utilises consensus algorithms and cryptographic techniques to attain immutability, traceability, anonymity, security, transparency and decentralisation. On the blockchain, confirmed transactions are validated by all nodes and recorded with a timestamp. Transparency is provided by the distribution of the ledger between the members of the blockchain network. Security of the data recorded in the ledger is guaranteed and cannot be tampered [64]. Double spending was first addressed using blockchain technology. This technology is based on distributed ledgers and cryptographic algorithms. Every block in the chain is connected to every other block and contains a certain number of transactions that have been combined with and linked to earlier blocks. Typically, a first block is created, and when additional transactions are made, another block is created, connected by retaining the hash information from the first block. This is illustrated in Figure 2.4. Furthermore, it is challenging to add a phoney block or doubt a block's reality since these blocks are extensively dispersed throughout a distributed network without central control. Transactions acquired with these properties become unchangeable, allowing data to be kept on a Blockchain network without alterations or the ability to follow the history of the record [65].

For the purpose of mitigating assaults like Sybil attacks, every Blockchain contains its own consensus method for deciding on a new block. Based on methods like proof of work, proof of burn, and proof of stake, a trustworthy party may be chosen to create a new block in the blockchain. The smart contract is one of the important features in blockchain, it is a code included in the blockchain and can be automatically executed when the conditions are met. There are three known classes of blockchain: private, public, and consortium blockchain. A private blockchain is controlled by a single organisation governing the activities in the blockchain, such as those who can participate in the blockchain and are considered more trusted among participants. A public blockchain is permissionless, and anyone or entity can participate in it. Its highly decentralised nature has drawbacks such as privacy, security, and performance. A consortium blockchain is a permissioned blockchain built by a consortium with several entities. Entities in this type of blockchain are referred to as nodes. The consortium controls which entity or organisations participate in the blockchain [64].

The Blockchain is made up of many blocks that are connected chronologically and timestamped. The three components of a block are typically the data, the hash for the current block, and the hash for the previous block, which is included in the new block to establish the block order. The first block to be formed is known as the genesis block, and subsequent blocks retain the genesis block's hash along with their contents and hash. A mathematical function called a hash converts data into a condensed, arbitrary-sized array. The hash function generates uncrackable outputs, ensuring each dataset has a distinct fingerprint. When data on a block is changed, the hash will also change. If this happens, the hash recorded in the next block will differ from the hash recorded in the current block, making it impossible to connect the chain. As a result, the chain that follows will be deemed invalid [65].

The Blockchain and the block, which are made up of data and their most recent hash as well as the hash of the preceding block, are shown in figure 2.4. Any alteration to a block will render it invalid and cause the subsequent chain of blocks to become invalid as well. A hash function serves as a fingerprint in a blockchain; however, in centralised systems, the single-failure node problem makes it simple to alter the hash data. Therefore, a copy of the blockchain will be disseminated among all participants to avoid data alteration in a distributed network. A copy of every record in the blockchain is sent to each node upon joining the network; therefore, to alter the data in the blockchain, an attacker would need to obtain the consent of more than half the nodes to succeed. In addition, before a new block is put to the blockchain, all participants must confirm and approve it. Consensus methods are essential in this situation [66]. To guarantee the validity of the contents and hashes on the block, the other participants must verify the block. In the case of Bitcoin, a subset of transactions will be selected from a pool of transactions, and each participant will be required to solve a challenging mathematical puzzle to solve the proof of work algorithm. Once the puzzle is solved, they will create a block of transactions that includes the subset of transactions they selected and send it to other participants for verification. Before validating the new block, other participants will check the information and the legitimacy of the transaction, for example, by confirming the address of the sender and receiver as well as the Bitcoin that will be sent.

FIGURE 2.4: Blockchain technology.

Blockchain technology has increasingly gained popularity in a variety of applications such as auctions [67], mutual authentication, and IoT [2], which have been the primary beneficiary of blockchain technology's features such as the decentralised characteristics which allow devices to connect and share sensitive data securely in an IoT environment. These attributes enable the blockchain to provide the underlying secure storage and a trustworthy computational platform for authentication systems. Devices in a blockchain network establish trust through a consensus algorithm; this enables devices to maintain a digital signature and cryptographic keys (private and public keys). This aids the communication and transaction between devices in the network; the immutability of these transactions makes them tamper-proof on the blockchain network.

2.6.1 Blockchain Life Cycle

A node builds the transaction and uses its own public key to access its private key, which is used to sign it. The network receives this transaction using a communication mechanism. The next group of miners, called peers, choose a certain number of transactions to be checked and verified. The miners try to convince the network to approve the block they construct based on those validated transactions. In this stage, the miner who is qualified to produce the next block is chosen in large part by consensus methods. For instance, to include a new block, the Bitcoin network employs proof of work to require miners to solve a challenging math problem. To ensure that transactions are validated, this method demands a large payment from the miner. When a miner solves a challenge and adds a new block to the network, they receive part of the reward for creating a block in Bitcoin. Hash algorithms will link each new block to the chain so that all transactions in recent blocks can be tracked. Each block keeps a hash of its preceding block to indicate the order of blocks in the chain[65]. Furthermore, the quantity of transactions is demonstrated by their size, which varies according to the technology. It is possible to track blocks since copies of them are stored on all peers and ledgers in the blockchain network. The lifespan of a transaction and adding a new block to the blockchain is depicted in Figure 2.5.

FIGURE 2.5: Blockchain life cycle.

2.6.2 Types of Blockchain

Various forms of Distributed Ledger Technologies exhibit distinct approaches to ledger implementation. These approaches can be classified into three categories: permissionless public shared systems, such as Bitcoin; permissioned public shared systems, such as Ripple; and permissioned private shared systems, such as Hyperledger [68]. Table 2.1 shows the comparison of different blockchain types. The types of blockchains are listed below:

1. **Permissioned blockchain:** This blockchain is also called a private blockchain. It functions as a closed ecosystem, where unrecognised individuals cannot join the network, access its historical records, or initiate transactions without obtaining the necessary permissions. The entity's ownership is either a private individual or an organisation, but a centralised authority assumes responsibility for the management and allocation of licenses. The consensus protocol used in this system can be identical to that of a public blockchain or differ from it [69].
2. **Permissionless blockchain:** Bitcoin serves as an example of a permissionless blockchain. Here, there are no restrictions on the individuals who can join and utilise it. Any individual with the required computational power can operate as a node and engage in mining activities through the utilisation of mining software. The accessibility of a wallet allows anyone to engage in the process of writing data onto transactions if they adhere to the established regulations of the blockchain. The types of blockchain technology are characterised by their openness and transparency, granting permission for individuals to have access to data and information in the blockchain [70]. These blockchain networks play a significant role in facilitating most digital currencies available in the market; an example is the comparison between Bitcoin and Litecoin.
3. **Consortium or federated blockchain:** This blockchain uses decentralised authority by removing the concentration of authority to a single individual. Rather than authority being given to a singular individual, it is allocated to a collective of individuals or groups known as a consortium or a federation. Examples are two blockchain frameworks in the field of distributed ledger technology, quorum, hyper ledger, and corda [71].

TABLE 2.1: An analysis comparing different blockchain types [3].

Property	Public	Private	Consortium	Hybrid
Definition	Open to all	Within one authority's control	Overseen by two or more entities	Overseen by a single body using specific procedures
Permission	Permissionless	Permissioned	Permissioned (Pre-selected nodes)	Permissioned (Public and Private)
Energy	Energy usage	Environment friendly	Environment friendly	Environment friendly
Auditability	Trustable	Inadequate auditability	Trustable	Trustable
Decentralised	Yes	No	Partial	Partial
Efficiency	Low	High	High	High
Consensus Determination	Every miner	A single authority	Pre-selected participants	A single authority
Consensus Mechanisms	PoW, PoS, DPoS	PBFT	PBFT, Raft	PBFT

2.6.3 Blockchain Consensus Protocol

Since consensus methods uphold consistency and integrity, resulting in tamper-proof and immutable qualities, they may be thought of as the foundation of a blockchain network. To assist the more novice blockchain researchers, we

go over several popular consensus protocols in this section. These protocols may be classified into two main categories: voting-based protocols and proof-based protocols [72]. In contrast, voting-based protocols include Federated Byzantine Agreement (FBA), Practical Byzantine Fault Tolerance (PBFT), Delegated Proof of Stake (DPoS), Ripple Protocol (RP), Proof of Authority (PoA), Proof of Burn (PoBr), delayed Proof of Work (dPoW), Proof of Elapsed Time (PoET), Proof of Importance (PoI), Proof of Capacity (PoC), and Proof of Authority (PoA). Table 2.2 shows the consensus of their cryptocurrencies and 2.3 shows a comparative analysis of various blockchains.

TABLE 2.2: Consensus protocols and cryptocurrencies [4].

Consensus Protocol	Cryptocurrencies
PoS	Nxt, Gridcoin, Potcoin, Steem, Tezos, Ouroboros, Algorand, Dash
PoW	Bitcoin, Litecoin, Namecoin, Peercoin, Dogecoin, Primecoin, Auroracoin, Mazacoin, Monero, Dash, Titcoin, Verge, Vertcoin, Ethereum, Tether, Zcash, Ethereum Classic, Bitcoin Cash
DPoS	EOS.
dPoW	Komodo.
PoA	Ethereum Kovan.
PoC	SpaceMint.
RP	Ripple.
POI	NEM.
PoBr	Slim Coin.
PBFT	Tendermint, Hyperledger Fabric, Diem.
DBFT	NEO.
FBA	Stellar.
PoET	Hyperledger Sawtooth.

TABLE 2.3: A comparative analysis of various blockchains

Blockchain	Permission	Consensus Algorithm	Scalability	Transaction Rate (per sec)	Smart Contract	Applications
Bitcoin [73, 74]	Public	PoW	Low	5	No	Financial Services
Ethereum [75, 76]	Public	PoW/PoS	Low	15	Yes	Identification, Financial, Voting, etc.
Litecoin [77]	Public	Scrypt hash algorithm	Medium	55	Yes, OmniLite	Financial services
Bitcoin Cash [77]	Public	PoW	Medium	300	Through side chains (smart-BCS)	Financial services
Ripple [77]	Public	Ripple Protocol Consensus Algorithm (RPCA)	High	1500	Yes	Financial Services
Tether [78]	Public	POR	High	50000	Smart Contract	Financial and Transaction
Neo [79]	Public	dBFT	High	10000	Smart Contract	Identification and Financial

2.6.4 Benefits of Blockchain Technology Application in Edge and Fog computing

The drawbacks and challenges of edge and fog computing that blockchain technology can mitigate include difficulties with data integrity, scalability, security, and privacy. By enabling decentralised and unalterable data storage, blockchain technology reduces the chances of data breaches and cyberattacks while offering options to improve security and privacy. Furthermore, using its distributed ledger technology to increase storage capacity, blockchain can solve scalability challenges, thus guaranteeing dependable networks with less

downtime. Additionally, by providing a transparent method of processing transactions, blockchain technology may enhance data integrity and raise the general dependability of edge and fog computing systems[63]. Blockchain technology provides various benefits in mitigating different attacks and plays a pivotal role in improving security through these properties [80]:

1. **Consensus Mechanisms:** The blockchain's functionality depends on consensus mechanisms like the proof-of-work or proof-of-stake, which are used to validate transactions and check the integrity of the ledger [81]. These introduce challenges for potential attackers looking to corrupt or tamper with the data.
2. **Decentralisation:** Blockchain technology operates within a decentralised network architecture, where many copies of the ledger are distributed across various nodes [2]. The decentralised nature of the blockchain network presents challenges for assailants looking to compromise the entire system.
3. **Encryption:** Distributed ledgers use encryption methods to ensure data security. This measure guarantees data security in the event of an unauthorised individual gaining unauthorised access to the ledger. The data contained will remain safeguarded through encryption, rendering it unusable [82].
4. **Immutable Record:** Blockchain technology offers an unalterable log of transactions, thus presenting challenges for assailants looking to manipulate or tamper with the data [83]. This blockchain property changes the level of security and transparency involving data transmission..
5. **Reduced Risks:** Utilising a distributed ledger mitigates risks and drawbacks commonly associated with conventional centralised systems [84].

An example of a distributed public key infrastructure model within a blockchain framework mitigates the possible challenges associated with single points of failure and unauthorised access.

6. **Smart Contract Security:** A smart contract, characterised by its capacity to execute contractual functions based on set rules autonomously, is vulnerable to security breaches [85]. However, blockchain platforms such as Ethereum have taken steps to address these risks. Developers must understand possible attack vectors, such as re-entrancy attacks, and undertake appropriate measures to mitigate their occurrence.

In general, blockchain technology offers a heightened level of security and resilience in the management and protection of data. This is achieved through its decentralised nature, employment of encryption techniques, use of consensus processes, and establishment of immutability, effectively countering various attacks.

2.6.5 Motivation of Using Blockchain Technology as a Solution for Edge and Fog Computing Challenges

In fog computing, computational tasks are delegated to edge devices. The attributes of fog devices, such as their low latency capabilities, enable them to process information independently of the cloud server. However, the area of fog computing has some security concerns, primarily coming from trust, security, and privacy in its decentralised environment [53]. Blockchain technology has been the preferred technology utilised to mitigate the drawbacks of edge and fog computing. The utilisation of blockchain technology has the potential to reduce this load by reducing computing and network costs while also achieving traceability [86].

The blockchain is a decentralised ledger system, enabling several computers to store the ledger globally [18]. This grants all participants of the network the ability to access transaction entries from any location in near real-time. The inherent attribute of a distributed ledger provides significant challenges for any entity, including assailants seeking to gain control over a blockchain network. The unique properties of blockchain technology, including transparency, secure encryption, reliability, mutual authentication across nodes, the utilisation of a distributed encrypted ledger, and a distributed database for executing tasks, could potentially offer advantages in edge and fog computing [87]. Integrating blockchain technology has several benefits that improve significant data security and privacy, improve data integrity, enable real-time data analytics, facilitate data sharing, and enhance the quality of big data overall, which would give fog computing an advantage and mitigate some limitations and drawbacks.

Blockchain technology presents promising methods to mitigate the security concerns in edge and fog computing. The following are applications of blockchain technology

2.6.6 Related Works Highlighting the Application of Blockchain Technology in Edge and Fog Computing

Bubbles of trust was proposed [88] for the purpose of authentication and identification of IoT devices using a decentralised system. Utilising blockchain technology can secure data integrity and availability using virtual zones. Servers and devices within the virtual zones can independently verify and identify each other. The importance of the system and possible target for attack makes security important for these virtual zones. A blockchain-based secure

authentication system was developed [89] to ease secure cross-communication between multiple bubbles of trusted IoTs. Hence, the approach offers decentralised trust and authentication mechanisms for edge devices without centralised authorities, improving authentication and secure data communication with data integrity and non-repudiation. Two software agents were proposed [90], namely the Software Agent for Network Formation and Monitoring and the Software Agent for Blockchain Formation and Monitoring. These agents were intended to be deployed in a fog node, where the Software Agent for the Network is responsible for forming and monitoring the network of Internet of Things (IoT) devices. On the other hand, the Software Agent for Blockchain was designed to implement a security framework for the integration of blockchain technology. A Fog computing system [91], which utilises blockchain technology for the purpose of activity recognition, was proposed for e-healthcare services. The framework employs a methodology for the purpose of identifying and analysing human activities and aims to tackle the various challenges associated with activity recognition in e-healthcare services, including data privacy and security challenges. The framework can potentially enhance the precision and effectiveness of activity recognition in e-healthcare services.

FogAuthChain [2] was proposed as a decentralised mutual authentication scheme using blockchain technology that authenticates devices independently without trusted third parties. This was designed to use an ethereum smart contract to execute mutual authentication between fog devices using their secure keys. The main objective of this scheme was to secure fog devices from unauthorised users while maintaining user privacy. However, the initial challenges faced before the introduction of this scheme were secure communication, privacy, and validation due to the different ownership or possession of fog devices. This scheme was limited to the use of stored keys and location for

device authentication purposes, which is an improvement on [88]. In order to offer a more secure, dependable, and robust fault tolerance, BlockAuth [92], a blockchain-based decentralised authentication technique, was presented in edge and Internet of Things environments. Each edge device is viewed as a node to establish a blockchain network. For the purpose of assessing the viability, security, and performance of the blockchain-based authentication platform, a safe registration and authentication method was created based on blockchain technology, and blockchain consensus and innovative contract development. A scheme FogHA [15] was developed to enable mutual authentication and key agreement between the mobile device and the nearby fog node. FogHA offers excellent handover efficiency since it just makes use of simple cryptographic primitives and does away with duplicate authentication messages using fog nodes. Anonymity, low latency, traceability, and the ability to fend off access compromise and privileged-insider attacks are just a few other appealing features that FogHA offers.

A Fog Computing architectural framework was proposed to tackle the challenges in smart neighbourhoods inside smart grid systems [93]. The primary objective of the proposed architecture was to achieve real-time control and monitoring capabilities for smart grid operations. Additionally, it aimed to establish a scalable and distributed architecture for the smart grid, ensuring the security and privacy of its operations. The architecture also focused on effectively managing network bandwidth and traffic and ensuring reliability in smart grid operations to prevent power outages. Furthermore, it also facilitates the integration of distributed power generation and renewable energy sources, optimising the performance of the smart grid and minimising losses. A blockchain-based solution [94] was proposed with the aim of improving the security and privacy in virtual circuit-based device data. Their model was

implemented in an IoT-based application in a virtual vehicle monitoring system. This system stores information about vehicle reaction, authentication, and integrity in the cloud platform and further stores the data on a public Ethereum blockchain to enable smooth transactions. A fog-based service was proposed [95] with the aim of detecting traffic congestion in a vehicular ad hoc network (VANET) by analysing a continuous data stream. The proposed system employs fog computing to mitigate data processing at the network edge and identify traffic congestion by collecting traffic flow data from the geographic positions of all cars. The performance of the system is assessed through the utilisation of a real-world dataset. Their findings demonstrate that the system exhibits a notable capability to detect instances of traffic congestion accurately.

A decentralised system [96] was proposed for fog computing that functions without the involvement of a third party. This system, blockchain-based secured key management in a fog computing environment (BSKM-FC), utilised elliptic curve cryptography (ECC) for secure data sharing and a one-way hash chain to generate private and public key pairs. The limitation of this research was its foundational assumption that the fog server is pre-initialised and inherently trusted, negating the need for external verification. An identity management mechanism was developed to keep devices anonymous and securely negotiate session keys through authentication [97]. Trust was not restricted to a single domain, and blockchain technology was used for authentication. As a result, it could be exploited by rough devices or adversaries to authenticate devices on different administrative domains without knowing their identities. A cross-domain self-sovereign identity management system rooted in smart contracts was introduced [98]. The system encompasses the entire identity lifecycle, addressing cross-domain applications and recovery. The suggested blockchain-based data storage technique to secure user data

privacy. A drawback, however, is the system's use of the ISC address as the UUID, making it non-intuitive for human reading.

The schemes and systems mentioned in this section focused mainly on authentication and the use of blockchain in fog environments and IoT. However, some schemes and systems have limitations as a result of the use of a centralised database or the use of a trusted third party. While authentication methods such as password-based authentication are considered non-practical in a decentralised system, some of the mentioned proposed schemes were not focused on user authentication in a decentralised database, and the schemes that utilised blockchain technology focused on biometric authentication and peer-to-peer communication between devices. Table 2.4 summarises the existing works for decentralised, multi and mutual authentication techniques.

2.6.7 Limitations of Blockchain Technology Application in Edge and Fog Computing

When developing and implementing privacy protection solutions for edge and fog computing, it is essential to take into account and consider the drawbacks associated with these technologies. There are several drawbacks to the deployment of blockchain technology in fog computing for secure authentication, privacy and protection. These limitations are:

1. **Scalability Challenges:** The scalability of blockchain technology is recognised as a concern, particularly in relation to its ability to manage volumes of transactions effectively. The integration of blockchain technology with fog computing would have scalability concerns as more devices join the network, and a larger volume of data is generated [99]. The computational resources within blockchain technology are a significant

TABLE 2.4: Comparative analysis of existing work for decentralised, multi, and mutual authentication considering scalability and robustness of authentication systems and frameworks (Y = Yes, N = No, NA = Not Mentioned). (DM = Distributed Model, DBP = Data Breach Protection, Mutual Auth = Mutual Authentication, MFA = Multi-Factor Authentication, S = Scalability, RAA = Robust against Attacks).

Work	Distributed Model	Data Breach Protection	Mutual Authentication	Multi-Factor Authentication	Scalability	Robust against Attacks
Bitcoin [73, 74]	Public	Proof of Work (PoW)	Low	5	No	Financial Services
Ethereum [75, 76]	Public	Proof of Work / Proof of Stake (PoW/PoS)	Low	15	Yes	Identification, Financial, Voting, etc.
Litecoin [77]	Public	Scrypt Hash Algorithm	Medium	55	Yes, OmniLite	Financial Services
Bitcoin Cash [77]	Public	Proof of Work (PoW)	Medium	300	Through Side Chains (smart-BCS)	Financial Services
Ripple [77]	Public	Ripple Protocol Consensus Algorithm (RPCA)	High	1500	Yes	Financial Services
Tether [78]	Public	Proof of Reserves (POR)	High	50000	Smart Contract	Financial and Transaction
Neo [79]	Public	Delegated Byzantine Fault Tolerance (dBFT)	High	10000	Smart Contract	Identification and Financial

challenge with devices in edge and fog computing environments, which have limited resources. The computational demands of blockchain technology may exceed the processing power and memory capacity of edge and fog devices.

2. **Performance Challenges:** Consensus techniques, such as Proof-of-Work or Proof-of-Stake, are essential to facilitate blockchain transactions. However, it's important to remember that these processes could potentially introduce latency and may negatively impact the overall performance of the system. The blockchain performance may introduce drawbacks in fog computing applications that require real-time data processing [14].
3. **Energy Consumption:** Blockchain networks using the Proof-of-Work consensus mechanism demand computing resources that require a considerable amount of energy. Energy-efficient operations are a significant consideration in fog computing settings [63]. The energy consumption associated with blockchain technology would be a considerable challenge in fog computing systems with limited resources when energy availability is constrained.
4. **Storage Requirements:** The implementation of blockchain technology involves storing a complete replica of the whole blockchain on every node that is an active participant in the network [100]. In edge computing, the computational and storage limitations of edge devices can pose a challenge to the demands of blockchain technology.
5. **Lack of Standards and Laws:** The combination of blockchain technology with edge and fog computing may encounter challenges rising from the absence of universally accepted standards and regulatory frameworks [38]. The lack of well-defined legal frameworks may delay the implementation and integration of blockchain technology in edge and fog

computing systems. This can pose challenges in the development of interoperable systems that can be integrated effectively.

6. **Security Risks:** Although blockchain technology possesses unique security properties, it still has weaknesses and is vulnerable to attacks [101]. The integration of blockchain technology with fog computing could add increased methods for attacks and other security challenges that demand attention and resolution.
7. **Complexity and Development Costs:** The implementation and maintenance of blockchain technology within edge and fog computing environments can present challenges of complexity and cost [102]. The utilisation of blockchain technology may give way to potential attacks, demanding the implementation of appropriate countermeasures.
8. **Latency:** Edge and fog computing are specifically engineered to minimise latency by computing data close to its origin [103]. However, the utilisation of blockchain technology may lead to an elevation in latency as a result of the time needed for nodes within the network to achieve consensus.

2.6.8 Mitigation of Security Challenges in Edge and Fog Computing through Blockchain Technology

Fog computing is a distributed computing paradigm that expands the capabilities of cloud computing by extending connectivity to the edge of the network, thus facilitating data processing and analysis in real time. The drawbacks and limitations of a fog computing environment make it vulnerable to attacks such as manipulation, man-in-the-middle attacks, and denial of service attacks. The integration of blockchain technology can potentially improve

security in edge and fog computing through the provision of a decentralised, tamper-proof, and unchangeable ledger that facilitates the storage of data. The integration of blockchain technology can contribute to the improvement of security in fog computing through the following methods [100]:

1. Mitigation the risk associated with a single point of failure.
2. Enables network transactions by utilising robust encryption techniques which ensure a high level of security.
3. It enables an efficient tracking of the status of edge devices and fog nodes.
4. It offers a solution capable of mitigating various attacks in edge and fog networks.

In summary, blockchain technology is widely considered a good technology for improving security in edge and fog computing through the provision of a decentralised, tamper-resistant, and unchangeable ledger for the storage of data. The integration of blockchain technology into fog computing offers solutions to several security and privacy concerns in edge and fog computing, such as data manipulation, disruption of services, etc.

2.7 Summary

This chapter comprehensively discusses the technologies, techniques, use cases, and strategies utilised in edge and fog computing. It introduces blockchain technology and authentication mechanisms, introducing the inherent drawbacks, challenges and limitations of edge and fog computing while discussing their characteristics. The chapter also highlights the potential of blockchain

technology to enhance secure authentication within edge and fog computing environments. Furthermore, it investigates recent research areas and related works, focusing on security, secure authentication and performance across edge and fog computing. The improvements proposed and studies highlighted have the potential to advance progress and innovation in edge, fog, and cloud computing by introducing fresh research concepts and opportunities.

Chapter 3

Securing Edge and Fog

Computing with a Decentralised User Authentication Approach Based on Blockchain (BEFCAS)

3.1 Chapter Overview

Based on the limitations and drawbacks in edge and fog computing environments, such as secure authentication, trust, data integrity, and privacy discussed in chapter 2, this chapter introduces the proposed authentication system BEFCAS, which capitalises on the unique attributes and benefits of blockchain and smart contracts to establish a secure user authentication process. The system incorporates various user credentials that have been selected to replicate a multi-factor authentication system; these include email

addresses, usernames, ethereum addresses, passwords, and data from biometric readers that register and authenticate users. These were picked in order to provide a multi-layered defence that keeps the login procedure usable but dramatically boosts security. By integrating these elements, a comprehensive authentication system that prioritises security and reliability while leveraging the advanced capabilities of blockchain and smart contracts has been developed. The outcome of this research has been published in the *Sensors* journal, Volume 22(10). An overview of the ethereum blockchain and smart contracts is provided below.

3.1.1 Ethereum Blockchain

The blockchain is distributed and built on a public, open-source platform. It gives developers the capacity to design and execute software programmes. This system is powered by its digital token, known as ether [104]. Additionally, it offers users access to the ethereum virtual machine, which serves as a platform for executing ethereum-based smart contracts. The primary components of ethereum smart contracts consist of solidity-written functions, events, and state variables. Using the Solidity programming language makes it ideal for creating smart contracts. When deploying a smart contract on ethereum, the process involves compiling the contract's high-level code (usually written in Solidity) into ethereum Virtual Machine (EVM) bytecode. This compiled bytecode is then included in a contract creation transaction, which is sent to the ethereum network. [75]. A distinct contract address identifies the smart contract following a successful contract formation activity.

3.1.2 Ethereum Smart Contract

Software applications running on a blockchain are known as smart contracts. Various types of transactions can be implemented onto the hosting blockchain using code written in different languages [105]. With the aim of automatically implementing the standard terms of conventional contracts, they are governed by the blockchain architecture. Contrary to conventional software code, programs have to follow context-dependent limitations. Smart contracts are self-executing contracts, or agreements, that are carried out by a computer program that, when it runs, enforces the contract's conditions. By entrusting the proper execution of a computer programme with the job of a central supervisory authority, institution, or organisation that both parties must trust, that role is intended to be removed [106]. A decentralised system run by computers automatically is. Therefore, a guarantee for such a program and blockchain technology is the means by which smart contracts realise the trust model they envision.

Smart contracts are immutable, decentralised, and public since they are kept on a blockchain. However, because blockchain resources are expensive, their code size is limited to what is allowed in each domain. A smart contract is said to be immutable when it is created and cannot be altered later. The components of an ethereum Smart Contract account are the contract address, executable code, private storage state, and balance expressed in ethereum virtual currencies [75]. Certain criteria, such as invocation data and payment in ether as transaction fees (Gas), may activate a smart contract by sending transactions to its unique address. The ethereum Virtual computer (EVM) is a virtual computer based on a Turing complete stack. To execute the smart contract code, it offers a run-time environment that is insulated from the network.

3.1.3 Application of Blockchain in IoT/User Authentication

A Blockchain-based IoT identity authentication system was developed [107]. The system used four steps to verify the identity of the user and devices. By following these steps, the user and device generate the key using the elliptic encryption algorithm; the hash value of this key serves as the system's authentication ID. Through IoT devices, the account information is registered into the block. Upon sending transaction information to the smart contract and receiving read permission from the device, the contract is established, and contact between the device and the user is created. There are drawbacks to this system; these include scalability, energy efficiency, key management, and practicality. Solving these problems would be essential to the actual deployment of such a system in various IoT contexts. Intending to improve authentication efficiency, [108] proposed a distributed and trusted authentication system based on blockchain and edge computing. There are three layers in this system: the physical network layer, the blockchain edge layer, and the blockchain network layer. As a result of this guarantee of trusted authentication, terminal-to-terminal traceability was achieved. While the system showed promising results, its real-world usability, energy efficiency, latency, and scalability are drawbacks.

A blockchain-based decentralisation authentication protocol called BlockAuth was designed to provide secure registration and authentication [92]. This scheme provided a decentralised authentication system with strong fault tolerance and high-level security, as well as blockchain consensus. Several authentication methods can be used with this system, including passwords, certificates, tokens, and biometrics. Scalability problems due to blockchain overhead and growing ledger sizes are among its limitations. Additional drawbacks

include latency and privacy issues on public blockchains and interoperability with legacy IoT devices. A mutual authentication scheme was proposed [109] based on one-way hash functions, and Elliptic Curve Cryptography. This scheme provides security and protection against cyber-attacks to the devices and entities that interact with it. While the mutual authentication scheme improves fog computing security, it still has drawbacks in scalability, performance overhead, resource limitations, potential security flaws, key management and device compatibility.

The issue of trust inherited by edge computing was addressed through a scheme [110]. As a result, problems were identified with registering and authenticating servers through trusted entities, as well as challenges posed by a single point of failure enabling threats to exploit the network. Through the elimination of public trusted entities within their network system, they were able to overcome challenges and difficulties associated with implementing decentralised platforms through permissioned blockchain technology. This scheme allowed authenticated users to access services without sign-ins at all service providers. This scheme offers a decentralised security solution for edge computing that shows promise, but it has issues with key management, latency, scalability, and resource usage. The system's integration with current edge infrastructures may be complex, and further drawbacks that must be addressed before broader adoption can occur include energy usage, expense, and regulatory compliance.

3.2 Research Contributions

This chapter introduces the proposed decentralised authentication system utilising blockchain technology and fog computing. It uses data types such as

email address, ethereum address, username, password and data from the biometric reader to register and authenticate users. With the characteristics and features of blockchain technology, such as a peer-to-peer system, cryptography, consensus and smart contracts, it addresses authentication using a decentralised database and peer-to-peer communication between fog devices (nodes). The proposed system achieves authentication and communication without a central authority. The proposed work has been published in the Sensors journal of Artificial Intelligence (AI)-Based Approaches for Developing Low-Cost Sensor (LCS) IoT Systems) [111].

The main contributions of this chapter can be summarised as follows:

1. Propose a secure decentralised user authentication that utilises blockchain technology, smart contracts and a secure ledger.
2. The system is designed to handle authentication requests using username, password, ethereum address, user email and data from a biometric sensor.
3. The system must guarantee the non-transferability of user data extracted from a biometric reader.
4. The proposed system is designed to utilise different authentication methods and data types for user registration and to simulate multi-factor authentication, which will be an improvement when compared to existing methods.

3.3 Assumptions of the Proposed System Model

This section presents the system model of the proposed decentralised authentication system necessary for the authentication of users. Before presenting

the proposed system in detail, some of the assumptions that are considered for the development of the proposed system must be outlined. These assumptions are commonly used in blockchain-based authentication systems such as [2]:

- The fog computing environment consists of mobile and stationary devices connected through several networks.
- The registered user devices or edge devices have access to blockchain technology.
- The fog device meet requirements to host the blockchain and act as a node or a server.
- The smart contracts should perform tasks of user registration and authentication.
- Nodes should not depend on other nodes to perform tasks.

A decentralised authentication system was proposed using the ethereum blockchain, smart contract, and ledger. In this system, fog nodes will serve as blockchain nodes and host a decentralised digital ledger where each node has a copy of the smart contract.

3.4 Overview of the Proposed System

3.4.1 System Architecture

This section describes the components of the decentralised authentication system using blockchain. The architecture of the system is represented in Figure 3.1. The proposed system components are described below:

- Ethereum Smart Contract:

The contract in this authentication system is deployed to handle the task of user registration and authentication. The contract would require information such as the email, *password*, and the *UserEthAdr* to enrol users upon registration and to authenticate users in the subsequent interaction with the system.

- Fog Node:

The fog nodes are devices that act as servers and blockchain nodes; each node has a copy of the *BlockChain*, *Ledger*, and *SmartContract*. The *BlockChain* information on each node is updated when a *User* registration or authentication transaction occurs on a node. The fog device or fog server must have enough or necessary requirements to host or to be part of the *BlockChainNet*.

- Edge Devices:

The end devices are user devices, and they are mapped to nodes during registration and authentication. These devices do not have the resources to host the *BlockChain*.

- Cloud:

The cloud is a large storage unit that stores, hosts and computes IoT data. This cloud server is tasked with processing and analysing data generated by IoT or edge devices.

FIGURE 3.1: System architecture for fog-enabled blockchain-based authentication system.

3.4.2 Proposed System Working

In the following, the core functionalities of the proposed authentication system is introduced.

- Initialisation:

All parameters of the authentication system applied by the user during the registration are initialised by the ethereum blockchain. These parameters are valid *UserEthAdr* (with Ethers or auth coins), valid *Usermail*, *password*, and *Biometric data*. The user *password* and *Biometric data* are hash with SHA256.

- User Registration:

In the registration stage, the new user is required to present a valid *Usermail*, *password*, and valid *UserEthAdr* to the *BlockChainNet*, these data

are validated and stored through the *SmartContract*. The *BlockChain* identifies this *User* as a valid *User*, the data provided by this user are stored on all *BlockChainNet*. User registration is represented in Figure 3.2.

FIGURE 3.2: Flow diagram for user registration.

- User Authentication:

In the authentication stage, a user sends authentication requests with *Usermail*, *password*, *UserEthAdr* and presents *Bdata*. The *BlockChain* verifies the *User* identity through the *SmartContract* and the *Ledger*. The outcome of this process depends on the data provided by the *User*. The authentication is successful if *User* presents valid details; otherwise, it is declared unsuccessful. The User authentication is represented in Figure 3.3 and discussed in the next section. In this proposed system,

a new *User* registers to the network with parameters such as *Usermail*, *password*, a valid *UserEthAdr*, *Username*, and *Bdata*. The data from this parameter are hashed with Secure Hash Algorithm (SHA256) and stored on the *BlockChainNet*. For successful authentication, the *User* must present data according to the parameter presented by the system. In the event of inaccurate data or failed authentication, the *User* is allowed another authentication attempt.

FIGURE 3.3: Flow diagram for user authentication.

3.5 Implementation

This section presents a description of functions in the smart contract that captures the working principle and pseudo code of the proposed authentication system.

Algorithm 1 shows the pseudocode for user registration request using the *EthAdr*, *Usermail*, *Username*, *password*, and *Bdata* of a new *User*. The *User* data are hashed and stored on the blockchain, and a new *User* is registered successfully. Figure 3.4 highlights the struct of the smart contract, the struct contains and defines custom data types in the *User* detail (*UserDetail*), these data types include the *EthAdr*, *Usermail*, *Username*, *password*, and *Bdata* of *User*. Boolean data are also used to represent scenario “isUserLoggedIn” and “true or false” binary results. The data a user must provide are included in the struct. During the registration phase, the *User* registration function is initiated to register a new *User* with data and parameters initialised by the *SmartContract*; the new *User* is required to provide *Usermail*, *UserEthAdr*, *password* and *Bdata* to be registered.

FIGURE 3.4: Snippet of smart contract code for user registration.

Algorithm 1 Pseudocode for User Registration

Input: EthAdr, Usermail, Username, Password, BData

Output: Returns True if registration is successful, False otherwise

- 1: if EthAdr, Usermail, Username, Password, and BData are valid then
 - 2: HashValue \leftarrow SHA256(EthAdr, Usermail, Username, Password, BData)
 - 3: BlockchainUser \leftarrow Store user data and HashValue on Blockchain via Smart Contract
 - 4: Log("User registered successfully") return True
 - 5: else
 - 6: Log("Invalid input data") return False
 - 7: end if
-

Algorithm 2 shows the pseudocode for user authentication request using the data *EthAdr*, *Usermail*, *Username*, *password*, and *Bdata* of an existing *User*. The submitted *User* data are searched with data stored on the blockchain; if there is a match, the *User* is authenticated, or it is unsuccessful if there is no match. During authentication, the user login function requires inputs “*UserEthAdr*, *Usermail*, *password*, *Bdata*” from the *User* to validate the data presented by the *User* through SHA256 as shown in Figure 3.5. The boolean variable returns a true value if the *User* identity is verified or false if the data presented by the *User* are not verified. The function `checkIsUserLoggedIn (address address)` checks the user’s ethereum address to confirm the user’s status on the network and returns a boolean reply. The function `logout (address address)` uses the ethereum address to end the user’s time on the network.

FIGURE 3.5: Snippet of smart contract code for user registration.

Algorithm 2 Pseudocode for User Authentication

Input: EthAdr, Usermail, Username, Password, BData

Output: Returns True if authentication is successful, False otherwise

```
1: if authentication request is received from the user then
2:   RetrievedData  $\leftarrow$  Fetch user data from Blockchain via Smart Contract
3:   if RetrievedData matches (EthAdr, Usermail, Username, Password, BData) then
4:     Authenticate user
5:     Log("User authenticated successfully") return True
6:   else
7:     Log("Authentication unsuccessful") return False
8:   end if
9: end if
```

3.6 Experimental Setup

The proposed authentication system is simulated through an ethereum smart contract utilising Solidity. This smart contract is tested, and the simulation is run through Remix Ethereum [112]. This IDE offers various features such as the creation, deployment, testing, and debugging of smart contracts, and it permits the connection of virtual ethereum blockchain environments such as Ganache [113] and MetaMask [114] through a web3 provider. The network layout of the system and simulations are executed in ethereum Remix IDE and Cisco Packet Tracer. Ethereum Remix IDE was chosen for this experiment because of its features, which allow for the development, administration, and deployment of smart contracts in a virtual blockchain environment. Cisco

Packet Tracer is considered one of the best tools that deliver a network simulation environment to create virtual networks [115]. The experiment is conducted using different ethereum accounts provided by Remix Ethereum and Ganache, each virtual ethereum account representing a user. Multiple user registration and authentication attempts are executed to analyse the metrics and each experiment. Data from the metrics, such as contract deployment gas, user registration gas, and user authentication gas, are collected.

Simulations are run through Cisco Packet Tracer to replicate the fog network with nodes and determine the time needed to send packets from user devices to the fog nodes. The simulation model is shown in Figure 3.6. In this, at step (1), User A presents data and sends a registration request through the edge device to the blockchain-enabled fog node. At step (2), the blockchain-enabled fog node stores user data on a distributed ledger, whereas at step (3), User A is registered as a new user. In the next step (4), User B presents data and sends an authentication request through the edge device to the blockchain-enabled fog node. At the next step (5), the blockchain-enabled fog node confirms User B's data are valid and exist in a distributed ledger. Then, the user is authenticated or denied. The transaction gas, execution gas and miner fees are recorded for both registration and authentication requests through the blockchain network.

FIGURE 3.6: The simulation model.

3.7 Performance Metrics

Performance metrics for simulations and experiments are detailed and presented in this section. This segment provides a comprehensive overview of the various metrics used to evaluate performance, along with a detailed analysis of the outcomes achieved. Many metrics are considered in this experiment, these are the contract deployment gas, the user registration gas, and the user authentication gas. The metrics are important for the comparison and evaluation of the proposed scheme with existing methods [1, 2].

- Contract deployment gas: The ethereum gas for deploying the smart contract in the virtual ethereum environment (the number of ether required to deploy the smart contract).
- User registration gas: The amount of ether required to register a new user in the blockchain network.
- User authentication gas: The amount of ether required to validate the identity of the user in the blockchain network.

3.7.1 Cisco Packet Tracer Simulation

The proposed system was modelled in Cisco Packet Tracer [115] with fog servers (nodes) and user devices to run simulations and tests on various packets and protocols (HTTPS, SSH, SMTP, ICMP), multiple requests on wired and wireless networks to obtain the time required to send these authentication packets on the network. These packets are chosen for this experiment because they are commonly used for secure communications over computer networks [116]. The system's network architecture created and simulated in Cisco Packet Tracer is shown in Figure 3.7.

FIGURE 3.7: Simulation of the edge and fog computing environment in the Cisco packet tracer.

3.8 Performance Evaluation

This section presents the comparison of the performance of BEFCAS and the existing methods [1, 2] with reference to user registration and authentication. These models were selected for their area of research and performance metrics. The BEFCAS can be identified with the blue colour, existing methods [1, 2] can be identified with orange and green colors, respectively. The system [1] is designed for user authentication, utilising blockchain-enabled nodes to carry out tasks of user authentication. However, system [2] is a decentralised mutual authentication that utilises blockchain and is considered an improvement on [1]. The BEFCAS system uses less ether (ethereum coins) when compared to existing methods [1, 2] in execution gas, transaction gas, and miner fees in both registration and authentication scenarios. The performance evaluation of BEFCAS demonstrated that the system scales nicely within the increasing number of authentication requests without having a significant effect on

the execution time, execution gas, transaction gas and miner fees. This is a result of the implementation of efficient algorithm to reduce computational complexity and minimising complex computations within smart contract architecture. The experiment is executed with four groups of user's devices: 5, 10, 15, and 20 user devices. The results from simulations in an ethereum blockchain environment are discussed below.

3.8.1 User Registration

Figure 3.8 displays the transaction gas, and it decreased by 30 to 40%. Figure 4.7 displays execution gas, and it decreased by 30 to 40%, and Figure 3.10 displays a miner fees decrease of 10% for a group of 5 users, 60% in the group of 10 and over 70% in the group of 15 and 20 users when compared to the metrics from the existing methods [1, 2]. In BEFCAS, different factors contributed to the reduction in miner fees during registration, these factors include a reduced overhead of multiple transactions and the batching of multiple transactions into a single transaction in the smart contract function. The gas of registering one user through the smart contract is 698,326 ether, and the miner fee is 0.0011.

FIGURE 3.8: Comparison of experimental results of the proposed system and existing systems [1] and [2] on registration transaction gas.

FIGURE 3.9: Comparison of experimental results of the proposed system and existing systems [1] and [2] on registration execution gas.

FIGURE 3.10: Comparison of experimental results of the proposed system and existing systems [1] and [2] on registration miner fees.

3.8.2 User Authentication

Figure 3.11 displays the 40% decrease in transaction gas in all user groups, figure 4.8 displays the 40% decrease in execution gas in all user groups and figure 3.13 displays the miner fees 30% reduction in the group of 5 users, a decreased by 30% in the group of 10 users, and a decrease of over 30 and 50% in the groups of 15 and 20 users when compared to existing methods [1, 2]. In BEFCAS, different factors contributed to the reduction in miner fees during authentication, these factors include a reduced overhead of multiple transactions and the batching of multiple transactions into a single transaction in the smart contract function. The ethereum gas for authenticating one user through the smart contract is 140,885 ether, and the miner fee is 0.0007.

FIGURE 3.11: Comparison of experimental results of the proposed system and existing systems [1] and [2] on authentication transaction gas.

FIGURE 3.12: Comparison of experimental results of the proposed system and existing systems [1] and [2] on authentication execution gas.

FIGURE 3.13: Comparison of experimental results of the proposed system and existing systems [1] and [2] on authentication miner fees.

3.8.3 Simulation Results in Cisco Packet Tracer

The results for simulation executed in a fog computing environment in both wired and wireless networks to obtain the time required to authenticate several packets: HTTPS, SSH, SMTP, and ICMP from the user device to the fog server or blockchain node on the network is presented in Figure 4.6. The results showed that all the packets are delivered in 0.004 seconds in a wired network, while SMTP packets are delivered faster in 0.003 seconds in a wireless network, SSH packets are delivered in 0.009 seconds, and HTTPS and ICMP packets are delivered in 0.006 seconds. The differences in packet delivery times across the protocols in both wired and wireless networks come from a combination of network characteristics such as latency, interference and queuing delays. The wired network’s advantages in speed and reliability contribute to its overall lower packet delivery times compared to the wireless network under similar conditions. Results obtained displays the time required

FIGURE 3.14: Simulation results showing the time required for authentication and sending packets.

to authenticate different packets in the BEFCAS, this shows the system efficiently handles authentication requests quickly, can scale to multiple devices in a fog computing environment, and is suited for application on edge and fog environments.

3.9 Discussion

This section discusses possible attacks and threats on the BEFCAS and the advantages blockchain technology presents to mitigate these threats in an authentication system. A comparative discussion of the BEFCAS with existing works is also included in this section.

The principal security issues in IoT are deeply rooted in systems that provide authentication to IoT devices, services and end users. An increase in IoT sensors and their ability to interconnect, collect and be associated with user

personal data requires stringent security measures [117]. The conventional nature of the authentication system makes it less vulnerable to attacks, thereby making it robust. Utilising a combination of ethereum address, email address, password, and data from biometric reader or device makes authentication secure. It also makes the system more resilient to common attacks targeted to authentication systems such as password attacks, Man-in-the-Middle, and spoofing. IoT presents some challenges after integration with blockchain technology. These challenges are as a result of IoT devices' limited networking and computing capacity. The edge devices do not have the capability to authenticate users due to their limited ability to coordinate registration and authentication; due to this, registration and authentication are performed in blockchain-enabled fog nodes/servers using edge devices as input and data collection devices. Confidentiality is considered an essential requirement in an authentication system, this is realised through the prevention of unauthorised or non-recognised access to the data in a system, network, or device. A method to achieve this is the use of encryption and hashing techniques such as SSL and SHA256. The BEFCAS utilised SHA256 to hash the user data; this transforms the data into a secure, unreadable format that is readable without a secret key. Similar to confidentiality, integrity is an essential characteristic of a good access-controlled or access-restricted environment. This is necessary to mitigate or evade the modification or tampering of data to make the system secure against attacks such as replay and Man-in-the-Middle attacks. The encryption of messages mitigates these attacks.

The use of blockchain technology in an authentication system without relying on a third party makes BEFCAS robust and resistant to attacks. Blockchain generally provides high-level security for authentication systems and the fog computing environment [100]. This high-level security encompasses data confidentiality through secure encryption, data integration through

credibility and traceability, data availability through distributed and remote access, access control through user authorisation, trust through secure communication and mitigation of attacks and preserves user identity through data and identity privacy [118]. The BEFCAS depends on the unique properties of blockchain technology for security. This mitigates vulnerabilities in SSH. Although SSH has its advantages and provides robust authentication, it does not give traceability or trust and is vulnerable to attacks such as connection hijacking, Man-in-the-Middle attacks, IP spoofing and connection hijacking [119]. The use of blockchain technology would mitigate threats and provide security, traceability, trust, and anonymity, and the BEFCAS' reliance on blockchain technology will make it robust against common authentication attacks.

Utilising blockchain technology makes BEFCAS robust against Denial-of-Service attacks (DoS) by storing user data, mappings, and other records in a distributed and decentralised ethereum ledger. Blockchain's provision of anonymity and privacy makes authentication secure and offers security for sensitive user data. The resilience and global distribution of ethereum's public ledger make it resistant to several attacks (DoS inclusive)—the ledger is shared and protected by various nodes where these data and records are hosted with integrity. Generally, the unique characteristics of blockchain technology provide extra security measures to authentication systems, IoT, and cloud devices. Possible vulnerabilities in smart contract code can pose a risk to the system and users of the contract. Vulnerabilities in Solidity open up the possibility of taking over control of untrusted functions in another smart contract; this is commonly known as a re-entrancy attack. During this attack, smart contract 1 calls an unspecified function from smart contract 2, which could give way to calling a function from smart contract 2 with a malicious aim. The BEFCAS addresses this concern by deploying smart contracts with

essential functionalities (code) and removing auxiliary functions.

Finally, the BEFCAS can potentially scale to multiple IoT devices and can still carry out the tasks of user registration and authentication. Results also highlighted that the proposed system, when compared to existing methods[1, 2], used fewer resources(ether) in execution and transaction gas during registration and authentication. During user registration, the transaction gas decreased by 30% when compared to [1] and 40%, when compared to [18], execution gas decreased by 30% when compared to [1] and 40%, when compared to [18] in all user groups. Miner fees decreased by 10% when compared to [1] and 20% when compared to [18] for the group of 5 users, and decreased by 60% when compared to [1] and 70% when compared to [18] in the group of 10, and decreased by over 70% when compared to [1] and 90% when compared to [18] in the group of 15 and 20 users. During user authentication, the transaction gas decreased by 80% when compared to [1] and 90% when compared to [18], execution gas decreased by 80% when compared to [1] and 90% when compared to [18] in all user groups. Miner fees decreased by 40% when compared to [1] and about 50% when compared to [18] for the group of 5 users, and decreased by 30% when compared to [1] and 40% when compared to [18] in the group of 10, and decreased by over 30% when compared to [1] and 40% when compared to [18] in the group of 15. There was a decrease by 60% when compared to [1] and and about 70% when compared to [18]in the group of 20 users.

3.10 Summary

A decentralised user authentication system(BEFCAS) was designed and implemented using an ethereum smart contract, with the aim of addressing user

authentication in a decentralised edge and fog computing environment and fog computing security problems inherited from IoT and cloud computing. It provided a solution for immutability and scale-ability problems in fog computing and proposed the use of conventional authentication in a fog and a blockchain environment to achieve the distributed authentication system. Compared to other methods, the BEFCAS utilised commonly used authentication factors to ensure easy adoption in real-world applications. Experimental results revealed that the proposed method achieved performance improvement, used less resources in ethereum(ether) and could be scaled to more devices and relatively used less resources when compared to existing methods. In addition to this, the comparison of results with existing methods showed that the BEFCAS consumed less gas. During user registration, the transaction gas decreased by 30% to 40%, execution gas decreased by 40%, and miner fees decreased by 10% for the group of 5 users, 60% in the group of 10, and over 70% in the group of 15 and 20 users when compared to the metrics from the existing methods. During user authentication, there was a 40% decrease in transaction gas in all user groups, a 40% reduction in execution gas in all user groups, and a 30% decrease in miner fees in the group of 5 users, 30% decrease in the group of 10 users, over 30 and 50% decrease in the groups 15 and 20 users when compared to existing methods. In summary, utilising the ethereum blockchain can potentially improve security and secure authentication in edge and fog computing. However, it introduces limitations such as transaction execution speed and high gas. The next chapter aims to improve the BEFCAS utilising the properties of neo-blockchain.

Chapter 4

Blockchain-Based Secure Authentication with Improved Performance for Edge and Fog Computing (BASAF)

4.1 Chapter Overview

This chapter introduces an improved authentication technique BASAF, which leverages the distinctive features of the Neo blockchain [120] platform to improve the proposed system in chapter 3 by mitigating its challenges, such as transaction execution speed, high gas and high resource consumption. The motivation of using neo blockchain comes from properties and its ability to execute transactions fast and its support for identity management systems, making it ideal for the identification in an edge and fog computing environment. By harnessing the inherent qualities of the Neo blockchain, a reliable

authentication method that ensures both swiftness and security in the verification process was developed. The results and outcomes of this research has been published in Sensors journal, volume 22(22). An overview of neo blockchain is provided in this section.

4.1.1 Overview of Neo Blockchain

Neo [120] is a blockchain platform that has been designed with the objective of enabling comprehensive digitisation of assets and identities by utilising smart contracts, ultimately aiming to establish a smart economy. The qualities of the Neo blockchain, including its decentralised ledger, smart contract functionality, and consensus protocol, can enhance decentralised systems through the utilisation of distributed storage and peer-to-peer communication [121].

4.1.2 Advantages of Neo Blockchain over Ethereum Blockchain

The Neo blockchain has properties that give it advantages over the Ethereum blockchain; these advantages include [122]:

- Consensus mechanism: Delegated Byzantine Fault Tolerant (dBFT), which is considered an improvement over Ethereum's Proof-of-Stake and is more energy efficient.
- Hard-fork proof due to delegated Byzantine Fault Tolerant.
- Speed: Executes 10,000 transactions per second compared to Ethereum's 15 transactions per second.
- Quantum computer proof using Neo Quantum Servers.

4.2 Research Contributions

This section presents the contributions of this chapter, which is an improvement on the proposed work in section 3. This aims to mitigate the challenges in the proposed work, which include transaction execution time and high cost. These challenges give room for an improved system using blockchain technology with properties better than the Ethereum blockchain. To improve on the previous work, a decentralised edge and fog computing authentication scheme utilising neo blockchain technology was proposed. This improved system executes registration and authentication requests using data types that include username, password, and neo wallet ID, during the process of user registration and user authentication. The differences between the system in 3 and this improved system include the underlying blockchain platforms utilised, the specific user information required during registration and authentication, and the refined registration and authentication processes. The neo blockchain properties, including its decentralised ledger, smart contract, and consensus protocol, improve user authentication by utilising the decentralised storage and peer-to-peer communication between fog nodes. The proposed system is an improvement from the previous research work presented in chapter 3 and published in Sensors journal(Internet of Things) [123].

This chapter's major contributions are as follows:

1. A security mechanism with improved performance is presented for a fog computing environment.
2. The proposed system is designed to execute user registration and authentication and provide data security in a decentralised environment.
3. The delegated Byzantine Fault Tolerant (dBFT) shows improvement over proof of work (POW) and proof of stake (POS).

4. The proposed system can offer faster execution speed than other existing blockchain solutions.

4.3 Assumptions of the Proposed System Model

The system model, along with the experimental setup and implementation of the proposed neo blockchain-based authentication system, is discussed. The system model also consists of a few assumptions listed below:

- Through multiple networks and the internet, multiple mobiles and non-mobile devices are connected to the fog computing environment.
- Blockchain nodes are accessible to authorised users and devices.
- To serve as nodes or servers and host the blockchain, fog devices need to meet certain requirements.
- It is necessary for smart contracts to perform tasks that are programmed.
- A task can be performed by a node without relying on another node.

The proposed system utilises neo blockchain, smart contracts, and ledgers to provide decentralised authentication for IoT and fog computing. The fog nodes execute blockchain tasks and keep a copy of smart contracts and decentralised ledgers. The overall flowchart of the proposed scheme is given in Figure 4.1. The system starts with the procedure where a user sends the authentication request through the edge device. This edge device is connected to the fog node through a network. The fog node is part of a blockchain network and has access to the smart contract execution module.

FIGURE 4.1: Flowchart of the proposed system.

4.3.1 Overview of the Proposed System

4.3.1.1 System Architecture

The proposed decentralised authentication system BASAF(Blockchain-Based Secure Authentication for Fog Computing) is described in this section, along with the tasks they complete. The complex architecture of the proposed system is shown in figure 4.2. It shows the authentication system built on

the neo blockchain using edge and fog devices. The components involved in this architecture are described below:

FIGURE 4.2: Authentication system built on neo blockchain and fog computing.

- **Neo Smart Contract:** Authentication and registration tasks are executed by the contract in this system. The contract requires data such as *Username*, *Password*, and *UserNeoAddress* during registration and authentication and as the user interacts with the system thereafter.
- **Fog Node:** There are several fog nodes in the network that act as blockchain nodes, each having a copy of the *Blockchain*, *Ledger*, and *Smart-Contract*. A *Blockchain* registration or authentication transaction through a fog node updates the ledger for the *Blockchain* transactions. In order to be able to host or be a part of *Blockchain*, these fog devices or servers must meet the required specifications.
- **Users:** For authentication and registration to be successful, the user must provide valid data and perform a series of tasks. A valid *Username*, *Password*, and *UserNeoAddress* must be provided for these tasks.

- Edge Devices: During registration and authentication, these are the user devices with insufficient resources to host the *blockchain*.
- Cloud: Data are the main characteristics of the cloud, which is often described as a large storage unit with the ability to host, store, and compute data. Upon receiving data generated by IoT, edge, and fog devices, this cloud server processes it for analysis and processing.

4.3.2 Proposed System Working

The working of the BASAF system is outlined in this subsection.

4.3.2.1 Initialisation

As part of the registration process, a new user must apply all factors necessary for the authentication system to work. These parameters initialised by the neo blockchain are valid *UserNeoAdr* (with Neo gas), *Username*, and *Password*.

4.3.2.2 User Registration

To complete the registration phase, a new user sends a registration request and is required to provide *Username* and *Password*, as well as *UserNeoAdr*, to *BlockChainNet*, the data is transferred through the *SmartContract* and stored in the *Ledger*. The *Blockchain* identifies the *User* as a valid *User*, and the *Ledger* stores the data provided by the *User* on the *Blockchain*. figure 4.3 shows the user registration process.

FIGURE 4.3: Flow diagram for User Registration.

4.3.2.3 User Authentication

When the authentication phase begins, the *User* sends an authentication request with the *Username* and *Password*, and the *User* must also submit a valid *UserNeoAddress*. As part of the *Blockchain*, the *User* is verified through the *SmartContract* and *Ledger*. Data presented by the *User* determines whether the authentication attempt is successful. Valid data are required from the *User* for authentication to succeed. A representation of user authentication can be found in figure 4.4. In order to authenticate successfully, the *User* must provide data that matches the parameters the system requires. If successful authentication is not achieved, the *User* gets another opportunity.

FIGURE 4.4: Flow diagram for User Authentication.

4.4 Implementation

The purpose of this section is to introduce the algorithms for registering a user in the BASAF system, as well as identifying and authenticating the user. A pseudocode for registering a user using a *Password* and *Username* is included in algorithm 3. In addition, a new *UserNeoAdr* is created for the new *User*, and all the new *User* data are stored in the *BlockChainNet*, and the new *User* is registered successfully.

Algorithm 3 Pseudocode showing steps to register users.

```
1: function NEW USER REGISTRATION REQUEST(Username, password)
2:   if (Username, password = True) then
3:     NewUser(Username, password, UserNeoAdr = True)
4:     BlockchainUser (new user data stored on the Blockchain using the
       smart contracts)
5:     Log (New user registered)
6:     return true
7:   else
8:     end if
9: end function
```

A pseudocode for user authentication requests based on the data *Username*, *Password*, and *UserNeoAdr* of a valid and existing *User* is included in algorithm 4. By validating *User* data submitted for authentication, the *Blockchain-Net* determines whether authentication will be successful or termed as unsuccessful. A brief description of functions in the smart contract can be found in figure 4.5.

Algorithm 4 Pseudocode showing steps to authenticate users.

- 1: **function** USER AUTHENTICATION REQUEST(Username, password, User-NeoAdr)
 - 2: **if** (received authentication request from user = True) **then**
 - 3: valid user data and NeoAdr–stored User data in blockchain through smart contract
 - 4: **if** (User data and NeoAdr is user data stored on the Blockchain = true) **then**
 - 5: Authentication successful
 - 6: Log (“authentication successful”)
 - 7: **return** true
 - 8: else
 - 9: Log (“Authentication failed”) **return** false
 - 10: **end if**
 - 11: **end if**
 - 12: **end function**
-

FIGURE 4.5: Neo Smart contract working.

4.5 Result Analysis and Discussions

To assess the performance of the proposed system, several experiments and simulations have been conducted to evaluate the method. Using the C sharp programming language, the neo smart contract has been written and utilised to simulate user registration and authentication in a neo blockchain environment. Algorithms 3 and 4 show the pseudocode with steps for user registration and authentication, and Figure 4.5 shows the working of the smart contract. This smart contract is created and tested using the neo blockchain toolkit in Microsoft Visual Studio code [124]. The Microsoft visual Studio code provides the environment for working with the neo blockchain toolkit, which is used to create private networks, multiple users, and environments for neo blockchain. Furthermore, this environment allows you to create, deploy, test, and debug smart contracts.

The neo blockchain network is simulated in the Microsoft Visual Studio code environment, and the layout of the system is then simulated in Cisco Packet Tracer. This experiment was conducted using Microsoft Visual Studio code because it allows smart contracts to be developed, implemented, and deployed in a virtual neo blockchain environment. A virtual IoT environment and virtual network can be created and simulated using Cisco Packet Tracer's network simulation environment [115]. Each virtual neo blockchain account had a wallet filled with neo gas and represented a unique user created using the neo blockchain toolkit in Microsoft Visual Studio Code. Multiple registration and authentication attempts were executed, and the metrics for each test are analysed. The metrics are used to collect data, including registration and authentication data. In the present study, emphasis is placed on secure user registration and authentication. A working IoT and fog environment has been simulated using Cisco Packet Tracer, using nodes and edge devices to create

a virtual IoT and fog network. The performance and simulation results are included in the subsections below.

4.6 Performance Metrics and Results

In this experiment, several metrics given below are taken into consideration, including the user registration gas, the user authentication gas, and the elapsed time. It is necessary to compare and evaluate the proposed scheme with existing methods [1, 2, 123], these existing methods were chosen because they also utilised the blockchain for authentication or security in fog computing.

- Registration gas: The amount of neo gas used during registration.
- Authentication gas: The amount of neo gas used during authentication.
- Elapsed time: Time required for registration and authentication.

4.6.1 Network Simulation in Cisco Packet Tracer

The IoT and fog environment has been simulated in Cisco Packet Tracer [115]; this simulation involved a virtual network of fog servers (nodes) and user edge devices configured and connected in networks to simulate a real-world networking architecture and run tests using various packets and protocols. Multiple tests are executed over wired and wireless networks where packets are sent from edge devices to the fog server, from edge devices to other edge devices, and from the fog server to other fog servers. The system architecture created in the Cisco Packet Tracer is displayed in figure 4.6. In the architecture, nodes 1 and 2 are connected to edge devices (laptops and PC) through routers and switches; these are wired connections, while node 3 is connected to edge

devices (smartphone and tablet computers) through a switch and wireless router.

FIGURE 4.6: Simulation of the fog computing environment in the Cisco packet tracer.

4.7 Performance Evaluation

This section aims to compare the performance and results of the BASAF system with those of the existing methods [1, 2, 123]. Using the metrics of registration, authentication, and elapsed time, the BASAF and existing methods have been displayed and can be identified in the charts in this section.

The scheme [1] was designed for registration and authentication; this used blockchain-enabled nodes to execute registration and authentication. [2] is a decentralised mutual authentication, this used blockchain for device registration, authentication, and location validation. [123] was designed for user registration and authentication in a decentralised secure fog computing, it utilised blockchain smart contracts to register and authenticate users. The BASAF

system performs faster than the existing methods [1, 2], as indicated by the elapsed time. In an evaluation, it is observed that it is scalable with increasing registrations and authentication requests with a slight increase in elapsed time and registration gas. Four groups of user devices are used for this experiment, 5, 10, 15, and 20 devices, to compare with existing methods. For proper comparison and evaluation of results, experimental results from existing methods [1, 2, 123], which were executed on the ethereum blockchain, have been converted from ether to neo gas. This conversion was executed with the current rate. The simulation results for registration and authentication are included below.

4.7.1 Registration Simulation

To compare results from the simulation, the same metrics were considered in existing works [2, 123]. While comparing results observed over a 70% decrease in registration cost when compared to existing methods, as shown in figure 4.7. It is evident from figure 4.7 that users in all groups are experiencing a gas decrease compared to the existing methods [2, 123].

FIGURE 4.7: Evaluation of experimental results on registration gas for the BASAF system and the existing system.

4.7.2 Authentication Simulation

To compare results from the simulation, the same metrics were considered in existing works [2, 123]. The BASAF system generated over an 80% decrease in authentication gas compared to the existing system [2] and over a 30% decrease when compared to [123], as shown in figure 4.8. Based on a comparison of the metrics from [2, 123] to that of result in figure 4.8, it is found that there is an overall decrease in neo gas consumption in all user groups.

FIGURE 4.8: Evaluation of experimental results on authentication gas for the BASAF system and the existing system.

4.7.3 Elapsed Time

To compare results from the simulation, the same metrics were considered in existing works [1, 2]. figure 4.9 displays the elapsed time to execute transactions; the BASAF system used less time compared to existing methods [1, 2]; this decrease is up to 10%. Comparing the results of [1, 2] for five to ten users, a 20% decrease is observed. In comparison to the existing method [1], times are recorded as higher for the group of 15 and 20 users.

FIGURE 4.9: Simulation results showing the time required to execute transactions.

4.8 Discussion

Neo blockchain is reviewed in this section to illustrate its advantages over other blockchains, such as ethereum, and to show potential vulnerabilities. Security and secure authentication are common issues in IoT and fog computing, which are attributed to factors such as the ever-growing number of sensors and IoT devices, their ability to gather and manage data, and their connection to networks that require security [117]. The decentralised nature of the fog computing environment makes it beneficial for IoT and cloud computing; this ensures the computing and processing of data on the fog level, as a result of this offloading computation on the cloud level and reducing the time required for processing, transfer, and computation. Fog computing is developed to meet the demands of resource-constrained edge devices and sensors, which include secure authentication. Nonetheless, fog computing has

limitations, some of which are privacy and security challenges inherited from cloud computing [125].

In general, IoT, fog, and cloud computing environments can benefit from the unique characteristics and advantages of neo blockchain technology. Some advantages of the neo blockchain over the ethereum blockchain include speed, considering neo's transaction speed is 10,000 transactions per second, compared to ethereum's 10 to 15 transactions per second, and neo blockchain's instant block confirmation time compared to ethereum's six-minute block confirmation time [126]. In a nutshell, the delegated Byzantine Fault Tolerant (dBFT) of neo is considered an improvement over proof-of-stake (POS) and proof-of-work (POW) because it is energy-efficient, makes neo hard-fork proof, and provides a balance between scalability, security, and performance. [127]. Ethereum's relatively slow speed is due to its proof-of-work mechanism, which is a lot slower than the neo blockchain. The first mover is also a disadvantage of ethereum, with more learning from the limitations to build a better network [128]. With blockchain as the foundation for the system, it can be fully scalable, able to scale to multiple IoT devices, and is still secure as a result.

During user registration, the neo gas decreased by over 90% when compared to [18] and the previous work [123] in chapter 3, in all user groups. During user authentication, the neo gas decreased by over 90% when compared to [18] and about 40% when compared to the previous work [123] in chapter 3, in all user groups. Elapsed time decreased by over 80% when compared to [1] and [18] for the group of 5 users, and decreased by over 90% when compared to [1] and [18] in the group of 10, and decreased by over 90% when compared to [1] and [18] in the group of 15. However, in the group of 20 users, elapsed time decreased by about 20% when compared to [1] and over 90% when compared to [18].

4.9 Summary

This work creates and implements a neo blockchain smart contract to address secure authentication and other limitations in an IoT and fog computing environment. This included scalability, immutability, and secure authentication of fog devices in a decentralised fog computing environment. The present research also aims to improve on the previous chapter, which utilised an ethereum smart contract to provide a decentralised, secure fog computing environment. The comparison has shown that with the advantages of the neo blockchain, performance, speed, and security have improved over the ethereum blockchain. The experiment's results display that the execution time for the task is lower; in addition, the the registration and authentication cost, when compared to the previous work [123] in Chapter 3 and existing methods [1, 2], is reduced by 65 percent. The resulting evaluation shows that the BASAF system improves in cost and speed when compared to existing methods. However, this edge and fog computing system can be further improved by eliminating the need for multiple identification methods and requests, thus guaranteeing privacy of user data through the use of Self-Sovereign Identification. The next chapter investigates methods to improve the BASAF system and introduces a Self-Sovereign Identification system to improve the identity management system in a 6G-enabled IoT and edge environment.

Chapter 5

Self-Sovereign

Identification-Based Enhanced

Security and User Verification

Scheme for 6G-Enabled

Internet of Things (LAMAS)

5.1 Chapter Overview

This chapter introduces a Lightweight anonymous mutual authentication scheme (LAMAS) to improve the proposed systems in Chapters 3 and 4 through the introduction of Self-Sovereign Identification to eliminate the need for multiple identification methods and requests and guarantee the privacy and place the user at the centre of the identity management process, giving users the power to determine which data or identity information to share in a 6G-enabled IoT

environment. The proposed system leverages the intrinsic properties of the ethereum blockchain to develop a smart contract-based solution for registering and verifying digital identities securely to mitigate security and privacy concerns associated with traditional authentication techniques. The effectiveness of the proposed scheme is demonstrated via experiments and simulations conducted on the ethereum blockchain environment. An overview of Identity Management Systems, Decentralised Identity Authentication and Self-Sovereign Identification is provided in this chapter.

5.2 Overview of Identity Management Systems and Self-Sovereign Identification

5.2.1 Identity Management Systems

Identity management refers to a set of technological tools that guarantee that only individuals with the proper authorisation can access the resources they are linked to within a specific organisation [98]. It makes it easier to handle online identities and comprises tools and guidelines for using digital identities to represent and identify entities, as well as to access online resources across a variety of application domains. When users seek access to digital assets, their digital identities are essential for recognition. A proficient IDMS is required to oversee these digital identities and the related data and credentials. Various identity management models have been designed and classified based on identification usage and the need for cross-domain. These models include an isolated user identity model, a federated identity model, and a user-centric model [129]. The service provider is a vital component of the majority of identity management systems. While in SSI, the identification system's core

component is the user. The claim, decentralised identification, verifiable claim, storage, and blockchain are all parts of the SSI architecture. A claim is only an assertion regarding a particular topic.

5.2.2 Decentralised Identity Authentication

Unlike centralised identity management systems like Microsoft's Active Directory, which allow third parties to store and modify identities, decentralised identity systems will enable the entity creating the identity to own the identity information [87]. Currently, most decentralised identities retain a mapping between additional metadata, including cryptographic keys, and a unique identifier (called a decentralised identity) that represents an entity on blockchains. The tamper-evident and highly accessible (DID, meta) tuples of decentralised identities are directly derived from the benefits of blockchains. Decentralised identities also ensure that the genuine owner of a registered decentralised identity can only edit the associated metadata, allowing the user complete control over their data. Figure 5.1 shows an example of decentralised identity authentication.

FIGURE 5.1: Decentralised Identity Authentication.

5.2.3 Self-Sovereign Identification

Self-sovereign identification is a technology in which users or digital identity holders have direct access to control over their digital identities. The network's issuers and verifiers have the centre of control in both the centralised and federated identity models [130]. Self-sovereign identities give individuals more control over their online presence, yet they also demand increased accountability from them to establish and maintain credibility and privacy. As third parties do not issue digital identities, trustworthiness is attained by the individual getting third-party confirmation of the accuracy of the information in the digital identity. If necessary, the person must then provide such proof [131]. Self-sovereign identification can address present concerns with digital

identification. This would make the system safe, dependable, and interoperable and improve ease of use. This is accomplished by utilizing blockchain technology and establishing a decentralised architecture to reduce reliance on third parties [130]. In Self-Sovereign Identification, users have complete control over the management of their information. Instead of depending on a centralised authority, they can store their credentials on their devices and present them for verification or transactions. A hallmark of this identification technology is its role as a digital counterpart to real-world identification. The benefits of tangible identification are that the owner constantly possesses it (like a driver's license), it's both legally and practically recognised as legitimate identification (with the issuer's signature and owner's photo) and crucially, it's always exchanged confidentially between the identity holder and the verifier. Figure 5.2 shows an example of SSI, here the identity issuer (government agency) issues a digital identity to a user(holder), the holder uses this for age or identity verification when seeking access to services. An analysis of existing work based on metrics such as the use of SSI, distributed ledger technology, data storage, privacy and control can be seen in the Table 5.1.

FIGURE 5.2: Illustration of Self-sovereign Identification.

5.2.3.1 Verifiable Credentials

Verifiable credentials are lists of attribute values, such as name and birthdate, that may be checked. Verifiable credentials must be verifiable, as the name implies[138]. Verifiers must be able to tell whether proof of identity relates to credentials provided by a reputable issuer and that it only shows information that is supported by the credential.

5.2.3.2 Verifiable Data Registry

Verifiers and users must be able to confirm that an issuer is who they say they are. Furthermore, verifiers must be able to verify that the data relate to credentials that are provided by a reputable issuer[138]. To facilitate this,

TABLE 5.1: Analyzing existing work based on the technology used, distributed ledger technology, data storage, privacy and control, fraud and theft protection. (NA = Not Mentioned).

WORK	SSI	Distributed Technology	Data Storage	Theft Protection	Privacy	Mutual Authentication
FogAuthChain [18]	✓	✓	X	✓	✓	✓
FogHA [15]	X	✓	NA	NA	NA	✓
Basha et al., 2022 [132]	✓	NA	✓	✓	✓	NA
Blockchain meets IoT [133]	X	✓	✓	✓	NA	NA
Dechain [134]	X	✓	✓	NA	✓	✓
Almadhoun et al. 2018 [1]	X	✓	X	NA	✓	NA
Enge et al., 2022 [135]	✓	✓	✓	NA	✓	NA
Masfog [136]	X	X	X	✓	✓	NA
DAT-SSIM [137]	✓	✓	✓	✓	NA	NA
FogBus [12]	X	✓	NA	NA	X	X
CAB-IoT [17]	X	✓	✓	NA	X	✓
Umoren et al., 2022 [123]	X	✓	✓	✓	X	X
The Proposed work	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

issuers can register their identifiers and associated cryptographic keys in a verifiable data registry.

5.2.3.3 Decentralised Identifiers

The Decentralised Identifier (DID) document that results from the resolution of a DID may include cryptographic data, verification techniques, and service endpoints. A DID is not intended to provide reliable personal information about the DID subject on its own; rather, it is intended to support the holder's autonomy and privacy [139].

5.2.4 Benefits of Self-Sovereign Identification

1. Eliminates the use of multiple email addresses, usernames and passwords.
2. Eliminates the chances of fraud and identity theft.
3. Improves solution for secure identity verification and authentication.
4. Eliminates the effort of collecting the same data type several times.
5. Provides a digital and secure peer-to-peer channel which connects the issuer, the owner and the verifier.
6. The use of selective identity disclosure technology guarantees the privacy and control of the digital identity by the user, the user decides what information to reveal and remains in control of the communication with verifier.

5.2.5 Self-Sovereign Identification Use Cases

This section introduces some prospective use cases for the deployment of portable, decentralised, and adaptable industrial Internet of Things systems.

These use cases make use of Self-Sovereign Identification. This use case explains how Self-Sovereign Identification can facilitate more effective remote communication via the Industrial IoT. Remote interaction is the direct engagement between users/devices engaged directly and in real-time at predetermined periods without needing to be present in the same place. The use of remote interactions in communications between users and devices in the workplace today helps boost output and efficiency while reducing expenses and keeping people away from hazardous work environments. With remote interaction, these devices can cooperate or communicate with their system administrators and nearby devices [140]. The information needed to generate centralised digital identities for authentication, verification, and permission is provided by service providers to enable this remote communication and interaction between numerous Industrial IoT devices. Placing the centralised servers for Industrial IoT remote contact provides hackers with a compelling reason to administer the devices and gain access to confidential data. A solution to this issue is provided by Self-Sovereign Identification, which increases the openness of digital identities and offers a method to move away from centralised services.

”FogHA” a method that enables mutual authentication and key agreement between the mobile device and the nearby fog node was developed [15]. FogHA offers excellent handover efficiency since it uses simple cryptographic primitives and does away with duplicate authentication messages using fog nodes. Anonymity, low latency, untraceability, and the ability to fend off access compromise and privileged-insider attacks are just a few other appealing features that FogHA offers. Similarly, to secure a remote user authentication system, the authors in [141] proposed a scheme called ”SecFHome”. It provides remote authentication in fog-enabled smart home systems and secure communication at the network’s edge. SecFHome updates the authenticator’s data so that

it may simultaneously check message synchronisation and authentication for increased effectiveness. Another mutual authentication method for a fog user and a fog server is introduced in [142]. In this approach, the fog user and server authenticate each other and formulate a session key while keeping the user's identity concealed. In addition to using pseudonym-based cryptography (PBC) and the elliptic curve discrete logarithm problem (ECDLP), the approach uses bilinear pairing to create the session key.

A blockchain-based identity management and secure authentication method is proposed for IoT-based WSNs[143]. This approach ensures trustworthy communications within IoT networks, safeguarding both node-to-node and user-to-node interactions by leveraging a public blockchain positioned between the base station and the IoT cloud. To deter unauthorised secondary use of data, a blockchain-oriented system is conceived [144]. A mechanism for granting digital pseudo identities that aren't connected to genuine identity was proposed[145]. This approach ensured a non-binding interaction between users and the information model connected to their identification by utilizing the advantages of crucial derivation systems. A lightweight authentication system was proposed [146], this used asymmetric cryptographic operations and cryptographic primitives for fog enabled IoT devices. A novel security method was proposed [147], this makes use of the primary authentication to carry out quick, lightweight secondary authentication to guarantee seamless failover between fog nodes. A scheme to enhance a technique of multi-factor mutual authentication was proposed [148], this employed a nonce, a challenge-response function, and a variable response time that may be adjusted. The same procedure can be used for both fog and cloud computing settings using these variables.

A self-sovereign identity scheme aimed at reducing reliance on third-party

platforms and striking a balance between privacy and responsibility is presented in [149]. This method introduces a unique executable code, termed a digital avatar-i, for each individual. This enables individuals to interact in cyberspace without the need for third-party applications. The integration of biometrics amplifies uniqueness and grants users greater control over their identity. A cross-domain self-sovereign identity management system rooted in smart contracts was proposed [98]. This system encompasses the entire identity lifecycle, addressing cross-domain applications and recovery. The authors suggest a blockchain-based data storage technique to safeguard user data privacy. A drawback, however, is the system's use of the ISC address as the UUID, making it non-intuitive for human reading. To combat identity theft and impersonation, a blockchain-driven self-sovereign identification and verification method is highlighted in [150]. This design diminishes the risk of identity-centric security vulnerabilities within the smart grid.

5.3 Research Contributions

A system is proposed to improve user identity verification and data security and to eliminate the need for multiple identification methods and requests in 6G-enabled IoT environment. The proposed scheme leverages the properties of the Ethereum blockchain to develop a smart contract-based solution for registering and verifying digital identities securely to mitigate security and privacy concerns associated with traditional authentication techniques. Ethereum blockchain was chosen for its consensus mechanism, which supports more decentralised applications. The main contributions of this chapter can be summarised as follows:

1. Propose user verification and data security in 6G-enabled IoT and edge environment.
2. The system is designed to handle identity registration and verification through an ethereum smart contract.
3. The system is designed to guarantee the non-transferability of and eliminate the use of multiple user data in a fog computing environment.
4. The system is scalable and can scale to multiple IoT devices.
5. The proposed system is designed to provide a digital and secure peer-to-peer channel which connects the issuer, the owner and the verifier.

5.4 Overview of the Proposed System

5.4.1 System Description

A decentralised user and data verification system (LAMAS) is proposed utilising self-sovereign identification and distributed ledger technology to mitigate limitations in edge and fog computing environments. The LAMAS system provides improved security in fog computing environments by giving more control of the user's data to the user and guaranteeing the privacy and control of the digital identity of the user. The system description is summarised as follows:

1. Propose a secure verification scheme utilising a self-sovereign identification method in a edge and fog-computing environment to eliminate the use of multiple email addresses, usernames and passwords.

2. Present a decentralised doctor/patient verification system that uses smart contracts and a secure distributed ledger. Smart contracts would register and verify patients in an edge and fog computing environment.

5.4.2 Assumptions of the Proposed System Model

The LAMAS system uses the ethereum blockchain as a secure distributed ledger, utilising its programmable smart contract to offer a solution for self-sovereign identification in a fog computing environment. The fog nodes act as the digital identity issuers and verifiers; they execute the tasks of issuing and verifying the users' digital identities through the secure distributed ledger. The issuer and verifier nodes have different tasks and thus use different smart contracts. Figure 5.3 provides a detailed illustration of the proposed scheme's overall architecture, including the registration and authentication of fog devices. The assumptions are listed below:

1. Mobile and non-mobile devices are linked to the fog computing environment through various network links and the Internet. These devices act as holders for the digital identity of the user or owner.
2. Access to the distributed ledger is only available to the register's node, the verifier's node, and the approved digital identity holders. However, fog devices must meet certain specifications to function as registry or verifier nodes and be part of or host the distributed ledger. Moreover, a registry or verifier node must be capable of carrying out a task independently of other registry or verifier nodes in the network.
3. Smart contracts must carry out programmed activities for the system to function.

FIGURE 5.3: Fog Node Registration and Authentication.

5.4.3 System Components

This section presents the arrangement and interactions between individual systems in the architecture.

- 1. Issuer Node:** Fog nodes in the network function as blockchain nodes that have a copy of the distributed ledger. They must meet the minimum requirements to host the distributed ledger and complete the tasks of issuing digital identity to new users. The issuer node can be owned or in possession of an organisation that has received a level of trust to deliver information, whether it be a business, certifier body, or governmental organisation. This organisation is commonly known as the issuer.

2. **Verifier Node:** The verifier node belongs to or has the entity to which the holder must demonstrate the veracity and reliability of his/her information, this entity is commonly known as the verifier. It might be a person, group, business, government, or other entity (i.e. a bank, or a university).
3. **Holder:** The holder is the user who is the owner and has control of the digital identity, as well as the person accessing an online service using this digital identity.
4. **Cloud:** The primary attributes of the cloud, which is frequently referred to as a sizable storage unit having the capacity to host, store, and compute data, are data. This cloud server analyses and processes data once it is received from IoT, edge, and fog devices or nodes.

5.4.3.1 Proposed User Verification and Data Security Using Self Sovereign Identification Scheme

This section covers the discussion of the proposed user verification and data security scheme using self-sovereign identification method for fog-based IoT environment.

1. **Initialization:** All factors and data needed for the user identification and data verification system to function must be met as part of the registration procedure to register fog devices and users or holders. The data needed are the fog device system information and the user's data, name, password, etc.
2. **Fog Device Registration as Issuer or Verifier:** In the registration phase, an organisation or entity registers its fog device Fd to the

blockchain using the device system information ($Fdname$, Fdi and Fdc), with an additional request to act as or carry out tasks of identity registration ($ReqIdIs$) or verification ($ReqIdVi$). The blockchain validates $Fdinfo$, stores it in the distributed ledger through smart contract and assigns a decentralised identity ($Fdid$), digital signature (Ds), password ($PwFd$) and digital keys ($PubK$ and $PriK$). The blockchain confirms the state of the fog device (Fd) as an issuer or verifier, and sends the credentials to the Fd . Figure 5.3 shows the fog device registration using the fog device system information. Algorithm 5 shows the pseudo-code for registering new fog device identity (using $Fdname$, Fdi , $PwFd$ and Sk). First it validates the credentials of the device. If these inputs are valid, a unique device identity is generated, and device information is stored on the distributed ledger, successfully registering the node. However, if any of the credentials are invalid, the input returns false, preventing unauthorised devices from joining the network. This process ensures that only valid fog devices can be added to the system, thereby maintaining the security and integrity of the fog computing environment.

Algorithm 5 Pseudocode for Fog Node Registration through Smart Contract.

```
1: function DEVICE REGISTRATION(Fdname, Fdi, Fdc)
2:   if (Fdname is a valid string and Fdi is a valid string and Fdc is a valid
   certificate) then
3:     NewFogDevice(Fdid, Ds, PasswordFd, and Fdc = true = True)
4:     Fog Device ID issue (Fdinfo and Fdid stored on distributed ledger)
   return true
5:   else
6:     Log("Fog node registration failed. Missing required information or
   invalid information.")
7:     Return false
8:   end if
9: end function
```

3. **Fog Device authentication as Issuer or Verifier:** During authentication phase as an existing identity issuer or verifier, *Fd1* wants to get authenticated to issue the digital identity of a new user. *Fd2* wants to verify the identity of an existing user or holder. Algorithm 6 shows pseudo-code for verifying existing fog device identity (using *Fdid* and *PwFd*). It takes a fog device ID as input and checks its validity. If the fog device identity and password is valid, then the fog device is verified on the distributed ledger. The verification status is logged, and verification is successful. If the fog device is invalid, a failure message is logged. This process ensures that only authenticated fog nodes with valid digital identities can participate in the network, maintaining the security and integrity of the fog computing environment. The output of the session and duration of time needed to verify identity or data. Figure 5.3 shows

the fog device verification using the fog device decentralised identity and password.

Algorithm 6 Pseudocode for Fog Node Verification through Smart Contract.

```
1: function FOGDID VERIFICATION(Fdid)
2:   if (Fdid is a valid string) then
3:     valid(Fdid = true = True)
4:     valid(PasswordFd = true = True)
5:     Fdid verified(FogDID verified on distributed ledger))
6:     Log("FogDID verify fog status")
7:     Return true
8:     Log("FogDID status ID verifier")
9:     Return true
10:  else
11:    Log("FogDID verification failed. Invalid FogDID.")
12:    Return false
13:  end if
14: end function
```

4. **User Identity Registration:** A user or patient seeking a digital identity must send a request to a recognised credential issuer (e.g. government department), the issuer requests the user submit the following data *username*, *date of birth*, *password* the issuer assigns a digital identity and an ethereum wallet, stores user's data and digital identity in secure distributed ledger. Identity registration process is illustrated in figure 5.4. Algorithm 7 displays a pseudocode for user's digital identity as well used for locating and authenticating the identity. During the registration of a new user identity, a new user sends a request to a recognised *ID issuer*. A new *user*, *ID*, *wallet* are created and data is

stored in *Ledger DLT*, and a new use *ID* is registered. Digital copies of the issued *ID* and other data are stored on *user* or *holder* device.

FIGURE 5.4: Digital identity registration.

Algorithm 7 Pseudocode for Digital Identity Registration through Smart Contract.

```
1: function USER ID REGISTRATION(name, password)
2:   if (name is a valid string and password is a valid string) then
3:     NewUser(username, password, ethadr = true = True)
4:     User ID issue(ID stored on distributed ledger)
5:     Log("ID Issued")
6:     Return true
7:   else
8:     Log("User ID registration failed. Invalid name or password.")
9:     Return false
10:  end if
11: end function
```

5. **User Identity Verification:** The holder seeking access to a service makes a request to the verifier, the verifier asks the holder to identify itself, holder submits data and makes a claim, the verifier checks the secure distributed ledger to confirm holder's claim, verifier makes a decision after check is complete. Identity verification process is illustrated in figure 5.5. The user's digital identity and data are stored on the ethereum blockchain network, which is also used to deploy smart contracts. To prevent data from being altered, each node in the blockchain network has a copy of the ledger and there are different contracts implemented for the registration and verification of user identity. The pseudocode for *ID* or *data* verification is shown in algorithm 8. An *ID Holder* seeking verification must submit required *Data* to the *Verifier*, the submitted *Data* is verified with *Data* in *Ledger* in *DLT*. If *Data* is accurate, *ID* or *Data* verification is successful.

FIGURE 5.5: Digital identity verification.

Algorithm 8 Pseudocode for Digital Identity Verification through Smart Contract.

```
1: function USER ID VERIFICATION(id)
2:   if (id is a valid string) then
3:     valid(ID = true = True)
4:     User ID verified(ID verified on distributed ledger)
5:     Log("ID verified")
6:     Return true
7:   else
8:     Log("User ID verification failed. Invalid ID.")
9:     Return false
10:  end if
11: end function
```

5.5 Performance Evaluation

In the LAMAS system, a solidity-based ethereum smart contract is used to develop the authentication system, and a remix ethereum IDE is used to execute the simulation. Remix ethereum IDE provides several functionalities, including the ability to create, deploy, test, and debug smart contracts [151]. In the simulation, each virtual ethereum account used represents a separate user. Further, to analyse the experiment's metrics, several user identity registration and verification attempts are made using the developed smart contracts. Smart contracts have been designed to serve the purpose of fog device registration and authentication, user digital identity registration and verification. Table 5.2 shows system properties and tools used to execute the simulation.

TABLE 5.2: Simulation Tools

Simulation Tools	✓
Operating System	Mac OSX 12.0.1
System Properties	16 GB RAM, 3.5 GHz, Intel Core i7
Simulation Environment	Remix Ethereum IDE 1.3.6
Development Language	Solidity
Blockchain	Ethereum

5.5.1 Gas Consumption

On the ethereum network, gas consumption can be used to estimate the computation cost. Most of the time, relatively high gas units are consumed while contract deployment and transaction execution. Transaction time has been evaluated under different contract deployment, such as one user, two users, three users, four users, and five users as shown in figures 5.6, 5.7, 5.8, and 5.9. Figures 5.6 and 5.7 shows the transaction and execution costs, respectively during the identity registration process of smart contract. While, the figures 5.8 and 5.9 demonstrate transaction and execution costs for the identity verification process of smart contract. In the registration process, results show a relative increase in both transaction and execution gas as user transactions increase, and a large increase in time after the group of three users. While the verification results show a relative increase in both transaction and execution costs as user transactions increase, and a large increase in time after the first transaction and a relative increase afterwards. The relative increase in both transaction and execution costs as the number of transactions increases, and with the increase in time can be attributed to congestion in the blockchain

network as transactions increase and the limited number of transactions per block, causing delays as more transactions are executed.

FIGURE 5.6: Identity registration transaction cost and time in seconds.

FIGURE 5.7: Identity registration execution cost and time in seconds.

FIGURE 5.8: Identity verification transaction cost and time in seconds.

FIGURE 5.9: Identity verification execution cost and time in seconds.

5.5.2 Latency and Efficiency

Latency is being calculated by analysing the time taken to verify a user’s identity. In the simulation, latency is calculated for user of groups 10, 20, 40, 60, 80, and 100. The latency comparison between the LAMAS system and DVASE [132] is shown in figure 5.10. The figure shows that the proposed scheme has low latency as compared to the DVASE. The delay increases with the increase in user access requests. The performance comparison of efficiency of Fog nodes is presented in figure 5.11, This shows that fog nodes in the LAMAS system have lower throughput when compared [152]. Figure 5.12 shows the comparison for time consumption with existing work [153] under different tasks, such as contract deployment, addition of fog nodes, and permission access. The figure clearly shows that the LAMAS system performs better when compared to the existing system.

FIGURE 5.10: Comparison of latency with existing work.

FIGURE 5.11: Comparison of fog computing efficiency.

FIGURE 5.12: Comparison of time used for different tasks.

5.6 Discussion

5.6.1 User Identity Control and Privacy

The LAMAS system offers selective disclosure and validated credentials. Users can limit the amount of data shared and increase user control and privacy by sharing only the necessary data and hiding the optional ones. Also, individuals have complete control over their digital identities thanks to their identity wallets, which allow them to maintain their data autonomously. Users can view a summary of the data they have shared and with whom in their digital wallet. The security of user data is ensured by the fact that personal data is maintained on a blockchain. Because a verifier does not need to contact an issuer directly during the verification process, the technique also prevents issuing organizations from tracking user interactions.

5.6.2 Decentralisation

In the LAMAS system, users take charge of their identity and information through an individual digital wallet. Unlike traditional models that centralise data storage, the method stores credentials in digital wallets spread across the network's periphery, granting users full autonomy over their personal details. Consequently, even if specific systems are compromised, there wouldn't be a massive repository holding the personal information of countless individuals, making any attack significantly more challenging. Additionally, the incorporation of distributed ledger technology bolsters data reconciliation, providing a trustworthy data record. Whenever user data undergoes alterations, there's a risk of data loss or inaccuracies seeping into the process. With a decentralised datastore, all participants can access a synchronised, real-time view of the

information. However, given their pivotal role in preserving and processing user identity details, the security of both the wallet and the distributed ledger required careful consideration.

5.6.3 Efficiency

The proposed user identification approach for edge and fog computing environment offers significant efficiency improvements over existing methods. Traditional verification requires a brief waiting period due to network congestion or the verifier being on a different network. Additionally, the verifier must connect to the distributed ledger, necessitating multiple levels of connections, which consumes extra time and resources. However, the LAMAS system can digitally validate authenticity within a short period of time, therefore enhancing user experience through instant verification. Moreover, the LAMAS system requires fewer connection levels between the holder, issuer, verifier, and distributed ledger, which significantly reduces application processing time. The LAMAS system allows users to choose which credential information to share, protecting privacy and reducing unnecessary data storage risks for businesses. Users manage their identity and data through digital wallets, avoiding centralised systems. This gives users complete control over their personal data and prevents the creation of a centralised data store.

Also, the system has only fewer levels of connections, as opposed to collaborative networks, between the holder, issuer, verifier, and distributed ledger, which considerably reduces the processing time for applications. Overall, the suggested method makes existing user authentication in an IoT and fog computing context more effective, dependable, interoperable, and privacy-preserving in multiple ways. The proposed approach has a number of potential effects on user identification processing and verification. Instead of giving all

data or credentials, a user can choose which information from their credentials to share. This protects user privacy and lessens the risk of any business or organisation storing data that is not necessary. The user manages their identity and data via digital wallets rather than conventional systems that keep data centrally, which is an added benefit. This allows customers total control over their personal data while preventing the formation of a centralised data store that might serve as a hacker honeypot.

5.7 Summary

In this chapter, a system is proposed to enhance user verification and data security in 6G-enabled IoT, edge and fog by leveraging a self-sovereign identification scheme under a fog computing scenario. The LAMAS system utilises the ethereum blockchain and smart contract technology to register and verify digital identities securely. By leveraging the advantages of self-sovereign identification, such as privacy, transparency, and decentralization, the potential to enhance the overall security posture of LAMAS has been demonstrated. This was done with the aim of addressing these drawbacks and the challenges in user verification and data security in 6G-enabled IoT and edge environments. An evaluation of the effectiveness of the LAMAS system was executed via extensive simulations and experiments conducted on the ethereum blockchain environment, the results show a lower time consumption of up to 80% as transactions increased during identity registration and verification.

Chapter 6

Conclusions and Future Work

6.1 Conclusions

This research aimed to address the problems related to authentication, data privacy and security in edge and fog computing. The key challenges include secure authentication, storage constraints, data privacy and scalability in edge and fog computing environments. It investigates existing solutions which aim to improve secure authentication. In order to address the research questions, this research proposed an architecture for secure authentication in edge and fog computing environments. The proposed methods address problems like immutability, scalability, and resource efficiency by utilising Ethereum and Neo blockchain smart contracts. Results from simulations show reduced costs in transaction, execution, and miner fees when compared to existing methods. The challenges related to authentication in the fog computing environment, as indicated in the research Question 1, have been addressed. These challenges include data privacy, secure authentication and the security limitations in fog computing inherited from cloud computing, which were noted in this research

in order to address Question 1. These challenges and limitations were identified in detail, discussing existing methods and highlighting the drawbacks of the existing methods. The research identified existing work and identified the methods in which secure authentication in fog computing can be improved, addressing Question 2. While these existing solutions offer benefits in decentralised, resource-constrained devices, they have limitations in performance and scalability. These findings suggest the potential for developing more robust solutions.

This research proposed a secure authentication system utilising Ethereum blockchain technology in edge and fog computing environments addressing Question 3.

The proposed method in Chapter 3 introduced the decentralised authentication framework utilising blockchain technology and fog computing. With the characteristics and features of blockchain technology, such as a peer-to-peer system, cryptography, consensus and smart contracts, it addresses authentication using a decentralised database and peer-to-peer communication between fog devices (nodes). The proposed framework achieves authentication and communication without a central authority. It provided a solution for immutability and scale-ability problems in fog computing and proposed the use of conventional authentication in a fog and a blockchain environment to achieve the distributed authentication system. Compared to other methods, the proposed system utilised commonly used authentication factors to ensure easy adoption in real-world applications. Experimental results revealed that the proposed method achieved performance improvement, used less resources in ethereum(ether) and could be scaled to more devices and relatively used less resources when compared to existing methods. This approach highlights methods that fog computing could benefit from increased scalability, immutability, and security. The experimental results demonstrated the practicality of the

approach in applications by highlighting notable improvements in transaction costs, execution costs, and resource utilisation. The challenges and limitations included transaction execution speed.

The introduction of Neo blockchain technology gave way for improvements, which ultimately addressed Question 3. This aimed to address the limitations in the proposed work, which include slow transaction execution time and high cost. These challenges give room for an improved system using blockchain technology with properties better than the Ethereum blockchain. To improve on the previous work in Chapter 3, a decentralised fog computing authentication scheme utilising Neo blockchain technology was proposed in Chapter 4. This enhanced system utilises data classes, which include username, password, and Neo wallet ID, during the process of user registration and user authentication. The Neo blockchain properties, including its decentralised ledger, smart contract, and consensus protocol, improve user authentication by utilising the decentralised storage and peer-to-peer communication between fog nodes. This showed improved scalability, better performance, shorted execution time and low fees in registration and authentication cost, further improving the system. Despite the proposed method improving in performance and scalability, the framework can still be improved by eliminating the need for multiple identification methods and requests, thus guaranteeing privacy of user data through the use of Self-Sovereign Identification.

Chapter 5 introduces a framework proposed to improve user identity verification and data security and to eliminate the need for multiple identification methods and requests in 6G-enabled IoT, edge and fog environments. The proposed scheme leverages the properties of the Ethereum blockchain to develop a smart contract-based solution for registering and verifying digital identities securely to mitigate security and privacy concerns associated with traditional authentication techniques. Ethereum blockchain was chosen for its consensus

mechanism, which supports more decentralised applications. Future research will concentrate on improving these features and exploring more Self-Sovereign Identification methods to introduce more thorough identity management systems in edge and fog computing environments, particularly in IoT devices enabled by 6G. Overall, the research objectives and research questions were answered; the framework illustrates the benefits blockchain technology can bring to edge and fog computing and the potential it has to be a valuable tool to improve secure authentication and privacy and optically manage and process data in real-time in edge and fog computing environments. The advantages of this framework are that it is fast, reliable, and can be implemented across different systems, provided that they meet the minimum system requirements.

6.2 Future Work

There are some possible directions for further research in this field. Blockchain technology and self-sovereign identity would be used in future research and development efforts to enhance edge and fog computing security. Using blockchain technology and self-sovereign identity, future research will aim to improve security in edge and fog computing technologies. Future projects will include the following:

- Examine more methods fog computing and blockchain might be integrated together for security, privacy, access control, and trust management.
- Study Edge-Blockchain systems' use of technology to improve privacy and trust, as well as low-quality data detecting methods.

- Explore the potential use of Artificial Intelligence in edge and fog computing environments for better performance and real-time data processing.
- Explore the potential use of IoT in healthcare, specifically in the early detection of illnesses.
- Investigate using blockchain technology to edge and fog computing settings for safe, effective data retrieval and storage and effective communication.
- Create a smart contract-based method for safely and securely registering and authenticating digital identities to mitigate security and privacy worries related to conventional authentication methods in an environment at the edge and connected by 6G communication.

It's critical to keep investigating and creating fresh approaches that leverage self-sovereign identity and blockchain technology to enhance security in edge and fog computing systems. In addition, future work will focus on self-sovereign identification and include utilizing edge device locations and possibly using artificial intelligence to improve edge and fog computing overall.

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